

UNIVERSITY OF CAPE COAST

**EVALUATION OF WILDLIFE HUNTING RESTRICTIONS ON
BUSHMEAT TRADE IN FIVE MAJOR MARKETS AROUND DIGYA
NATIONAL PARK**

NANA OWUSU-ANSAH

2009

UNIVERSITY OF CAPE COAST

**EVALUATION OF WILDLIFE HUNTING RESTRICTIONS ON
BUSHMEAT TRADE IN FIVE MAJOR MARKETS AROUND DIGYA
NATIONAL PARK**

BY

NANA OWUSU-ANSAH

**A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO THE INSTITUTE FOR
DEVELOPMENT STUDIES OF THE FACULTY OF SOCIAL
SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF CAPE COAST IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF A
MASTER OF ARTS DEGREE IN ENVIRONMENTAL
MANAGEMENT AND POLICY**

FEBRUARY, 2009

DECLARATION

Candidate's declaration

I hereby declare that this dissertation is the result of my own original work and that no part of it has been presented for another degree in this university or elsewhere.

Candidate's signature.....Date.....

Name:

Supervisor's declaration

I hereby declare that the preparation and presentation of the dissertation were supervised in accordance with the guidelines on supervision of dissertation laid down by university of cape coast.

Supervisor's signature.....Date.....

Name:.....

ABSTRACT

Bushmeat harvesting, processing and trade has long been a source of livelihood for many homes in both rural and urban Ghana. Since the general belief in the country is that wildlife numbers have dwindled over the years due to unsustainable harvesting of this natural resource, this study sought to evaluate the effectiveness of wildlife laws in controlling trade and harvesting of wildlife. A total of 227 traders and 49 hunters were interviewed in five major markets around Digya National Park. Respondents were selected through snowballing while the simple random sampling procedure was used in selecting market days. The main data collection techniques were in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The data were processed using the Statistical Package for Scientific Solutions (SPSS) and Excel software. Based on the major findings of the study, it was concluded that the wildlife restrictions in the country is not readily complied by the operators of the bushmeat trade. The Wildlife Division is not properly placed to enforce the laws while the licensing system does not require operators to produce returns on their purchases. The bushmeat trade is completely dominated by rodents constituting 80.3% of the total trade at the five markets surveyed.

The study recommended that to achieve sustainable bushmeat harvesting, the Wildlife Division especially of the Digya National Park needs to build the capacity of its field staff to coordinate and monitor bushmeat exploitation, production and trade in markets around the Park. Also the Wildlife Division management should strengthen the community collaborative resource management unit to carry out wildlife conservation education in the communities. There is also need for the Wildlife Division to vigorously pursue

its new Community Resource Management Areas (CREMAs), which seeks to devolve ownership and stewardship of wildlife resources to local communities with the view of ensuring community participation in wildlife management.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I acknowledge with profound gratitude to the support and encouragement of all the lecturers of the Institute for Development Studies, University of Cape Coast.

My sincere gratitude and appreciation go to Professor A.M. Abane my supervisor, through whose hard work I was challenged to work even harder.

I would also like to thank the staff of the Digya National Park, especially Mr. Bernard Asamoah-Boateng for giving me the opportunity to undertake this course.

I cannot forget my field team members who facilitated the data collection for the study. I am equally indebted to all the respondents for accepting to offer information for the study.

To all my EMP course mates especially members of my study group, Peter Hodgson, Daniel Nsiah Adobasom, Emelia Boadu and George Frimpong, I say thank you and stay tuned.

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my dear wife-Ama Aboagyewaa Owusu and my children, my late father- Opanin Yaw Manu, my Mother- Abenaa Antwiwaa and my god-mother Georgina Gyamfi. Thanks for your unflinching support in my education through diverse ways.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title	page
DECLARATION	i
ABSTRACT	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iv
DEDICATION	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vi
LIST OF TABLES	ix
LIST OF FIGURES	x
ABBREVIATIONS	xi
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	
Background to the study	1
Statement of the problem	3
Objectives	5
Justification of the study	6
Organisation of the study	6
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	
Wildlife as food	8
Wildlife as a source of income	11
Wildlife conservation	17
Community participation in wildlife management	21

Wildlife legislation and law enforcement	28
Conceptual framework for the study	31
CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY	
Research design	36
Sampling technique	37
In-depth interviews	40
Focus group discussion (FGD)	41
Direct observation	41
Desktop data collection	41
Data analysis	42
CHAPTER FOUR: BUSHMEAT HUNTING AND TRADE: THE ISSUES	
Introduction	43
Traders' demography and locations	43
Traders' classification on fulltime/part-time bases	46
Traders' classification according to seasons	47
Species traded at the markets	48
Conservation status of species traded at the markets	52
Species traded according to hunting seasons	54
Freshly killed species and their reproductive status	57
Traders' knowledge on hunting methods	58
Traders' knowledge on hunting regulations	61

Bushmeat licensing and trade illegalities	65
Hunters and hunting activities	68
Hunters' catch and how they dispose off their kill	72
Hunters' awareness of hunting regulations	75
Poaching activities at the Digya National Park	78
Hunting and bushmeat trade license revenue from Digya	80
CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
Study objectives and methods	83
The major findings of the study	84
Conclusions	86
Recommendations	86
REFERENCES	89
APPENDIX A	95
APPENDIX B	97
APPENDIX C	99
APPENDIX D	101

LIST OF TABLES

Table		page
1:	Towns and their market days	39
2:	Traders frequency and locations	44
3:	Sex of respondents	46
4:	Traders classification	47
5:	Traders classification according to hunting seasons	48
6:	Species and their biological families	49
7:	Conservation status of species traded at the markets	53
8:	Species traded at markets according to seasons	55
9:	Species observed as freshly killed	57
10:	Traders' awareness on hunting methods	59
11:	Effects of hunting methods on meat quality	61
12:	Traders' awareness on hunting regulations	62
13:	Illegalities of the bushmeat trade license	66
14:	Distribution of hunters by location	68
15:	Species harvested by hunters	73
16:	Hunters' awareness on hunting regulations	75

LIST OF FIGURES

Figures

page

1:	Bushmeat trade actors and levels of interactions	15
2:	A conceptual framework for evaluating wildlife utilisation restriction	35
3:	Illegal activities in Digya national park	78
4:	Revenue generation from bushmeat license	81

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

NTFPS	–	Non-Timber Forest Products
SSA	–	Sub-Saharan Africa
FAO	–	Food and Agriculture Organisation
CREMAs	–	Community Resources Management Areas
EU	–	European Union
IUCN	–	International Union for Conservation of Nature
PA	–	Protected Area
CAMPFIRE	–	Communal Area Management Programme for Indigenous Resources
CFWM	–	Community Forestry and Wildlife Management
CBNRM	–	Community Based Natural Resources Management
GSBAs	–	Globally Significant Biodiversity Areas
FGD	–	Focus Group Discussion
LI	–	Legislative Instrument
SPSS	–	Statistical Programme for Scientific Solution
P. Monkey	–	Patas Monkey
G. Monkey	–	Green Monkey
B.T. Porcupine	–	Brush Tailed Porcupine
M. Duiker	–	Maxwell Duiker
R.R. Hog	–	Red River Hog
R.F Duiker	–	Red Flanked Duiker

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Background to the study

Forests form an integral part of the rural economy, providing subsistence goods and services as well as items of trade (Boafo and Falconer 1997). These forest products are known collectively as non-timber forest products (NTFPs). Among all the NTFPs bushmeat seems to be the most cherished in the Ghanaian society and is the second most popular meat after chicken (Ntiamoah-Baidu 1998). In an evaluation of the Subri Forestry Project in Ghana, for example, it was found that 94 percent of those surveyed considered the worst impact of forest conversion to other forms of land use to be the loss of bushmeat in the area (Asibey and Child 1990; Korang 1986).

In sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) the proportion of wild animal meat in total protein supplies is exceptionally high. For example, communities living near forests in Nigeria obtain 84 percent of their animal protein from bushmeat. In Ghana, approximately 75 percent of the population consumes wild animals regularly whereas in Liberia it is 70 percent and in Botswana it approximates 60 percent (Asibey and Child 1990; FAO 1989). These high figures may understate the reality as wildlife consumption is often unrecorded.

In considering the role of wild animals as food, it is important to take a wide view rather than a limited perspective covering only large “game animals”. In fact, small animals generally provide the greatest amount of meat to the subsistence diet. Various types of snails, snakes and other reptiles and amphibians are also consumed. For example, in Ghana and several other parts of West Africa, residents of districts with concentration of snails are

considered lucky by inhabitants of other areas not so endowed (Asibey and Child 1990). Insects also often make a significant contribution to overall protein supplies. Apart from bushmeat being a necessity in poor rural settings, all people also sometimes eat it as a matter of preference, a luxury or as a cultural requirement reserved for special occasions.

The Wildlife Division of the Forestry Commission of Ghana policy on hunting is concentrated on the mandate of protecting the flora and fauna resources within protected areas while restricting the use of these resources outside protected areas. Wildlife management in Ghana is principally through a system of protected areas, a closed season and species that may be hunted. Furthermore, hunters must have a valid game license and a trophy-hunting license before an animal could be removed. Other hunting restrictions have to do with prohibitive hunting methods such as the use of wire snare and a gin trap. It is also an offence to hunt in a protected area without an authorized permission from the Executive Director of the Wildlife Division. The Wildlife Division of the Forestry Commission of Ghana has become increasingly concerned over the fact that the local people around protected areas do not legally benefit from management of wildlife resources and there is often a poor relationship between the Division's staff and the surrounding communities.

Bushmeat hunting and trade serves as a household income for many people and constitute an important component of the national economy. The bushmeat industry comprises a number of people who form the chain including hunters, market women at different levels (wholesalers and retailers), 'chop bar' operators as well as a number of helpers who depend on

continuous availability of bushmeat. According to Ntiamoa-Baidu (1998) the average monthly income for a hunter in the late 1990s was ₵185,560.00, more than three times the government's minimum wage and equivalent to graduate entry point salary in the civil service at that time. Annual volume of bushmeat harvested in Ghana by hunters is estimated at 384,991.8 tons, worth \$350 millions, while total annual bushmeat consumption is estimated at 225,287 tons valued at \$205 million. The total meat production from domestic source (cattle, sheep, goat and pig) for 1996 was only 38,535.3 tons while marine and fresh water fish contributed 490,000 tons for the same period. It is also known that some of the meat harvested is sold across the country's borders especially Togo and some destinations in Europe. This means meat sold on the local market is minimal and that the actual volume traded in is much higher.

Statement of the problem

The popularity of bushmeat in Ghana and the high demand for this resource put a lot of pressure on wild animal populations. The present state of the wild animal populations as well as the methods and the rate of exploitation make it unsustainable and this may lead to extinction of most species. A document on sustainable use of bushmeat by the Wildlife Division (1998) has reported a higher level of awareness of the closed season period for hunting and bushmeat trade restrictions in communities around protected areas than areas where the Wildlife Division is absent. Ironically, the same document reports the lack of awareness by most hunters and traders who must acquire hunting and trade licenses before engaging in bushmeat trade. It is also a known fact that the closed season regulation Act (Act: 685) is not strictly

followed as prohibited bushmeat is openly displayed in markets and on roadsides during the period.

The Forest and Wildlife Policy of Ghana (1994) aims at conservation and sustainable development of the nation's forest and wildlife resources for maintenance of environmental quality and perpetual flow of optimum benefits to all segments of society. This policy guarantees citizens rights to have access to natural resources for maintaining adequate standard of living. The policy also places responsibility on the citizens to ensure sustainable use of such resources. However, this policy direction is in conflict with most wildlife hunting restrictions. Presently, there are a number of laws in the country, which seek to regulate bushmeat hunting and trade. Some of these regulations and laws include the fact that all persons who capture, kill or trade in wild animals must obtain hunting/ trade license from the district assemblies. These restrictions do not consider the traditional use of wildlife for food. The capture of wild animals for food is considered as poaching and the technologies used for hunting are described as unlawful while the commercialization of bushmeat without license is termed as illegal (Asibey and Child 1990).

These restrictions have alienated the local people from forests management. Therefore, property owners have no incentives in managing wildlife as an alternative land use system. Enforcement of these laws is ineffective and this allows all species irrespective of their conservation status to be exploited all year round. For example, the regulations specifying a period of closed season from 1st August to 1st December every year, where hunting is not allowed on any species except the grasscutter (*Thryonomys swinderianus*), is not readily observed. The present rate of game license charges of ₵1000

(smallest charge) for grasscutter and ₵350,000.00 (largest charge) for buffalo, are grossly insignificant compared to the value in bushmeat trade. The penalties associated with flouting of any of these laws are also not deterrent enough. This study therefore sought to answer the following questions:

- How would a high level of awareness of hunting restrictions affect the rate of trade in bushmeat?
- Why would hunters use different hunting methods in capturing animals rather than the approved method of gunshot?
- Why do traders and hunters not readily obtain license before embarking on the bushmeat trade?
- What should the Wildlife Division do to collaborate with communities to ensure sustainable use of forest resources?

Objectives of the study

The study aimed to evaluate the level of awareness of stakeholders in the policy on bushmeat trade and wildlife hunting restrictions in Ghana. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- Assess the effectiveness of the present closed season from 1st August to 1st December in conserving protected species;
- List some major hunting methods and their effects on hunted species;
- Assess the major factors that prevent hunters and traders from acquiring licenses for their trade; and
- Determine possible areas of collaboration between forest communities and the Wildlife Division in ensuring effective utilization of forest resources.

Justification of study

At the end of this study, findings generated would be passed onto the Wildlife Division to use to improve the relationship between management of the Digya National Park and the surrounding communities. The Wildlife Division will use the recommendations provided to initiate new policies while strengthening the existing ones to enhance wildlife conservation outside protected areas. Until now, the Wildlife Division has focused on endangered and trophy species. The institutions of state ownership of wildlife, which centrally imposed licenses and restrictions on the sale of products, have created in most cases enmity between community members, hunters and bushmeat traders on one hand and the Wildlife Division staff on the other. The findings of this study will also be a tool for the management of the Digya National Park to enhance community participation in community resources management areas (CREMAs). This is a new policy direction by the Division to enhance wildlife management outside protected areas.

Organisation of study

The study is organized into five chapters. Following this introduction is chapter two, which reviews literature on protected area management, wildlife as food, wildlife conservation, wildlife legislation and sustainable development. The conceptual framework used for the study is also outlined. Chapter three covers the methodology used for the research work while chapter four focuses on the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents in the sampled markets. Various variables such as age, sex, number of years in

the hunting and bushmeat trade business and educational background in the data are assessed to determine the extent to which they know about the various hunting restrictions. Analysis of species killed related to their conservational status and the period within which they were killed would be carried out. Chapter five discusses the results obtained. The chapter also summarizes and interprets the results and provides recommendations for better management of wildlife outside protected areas.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A considerable amount of work has been done on bushmeat hunting and trade in Ghana especially in the 1970s (Ntiamoa-Baidu 1998) with Asibey pioneering most of these works. The chapter reviews issues related to wildlife management and conservation such as wildlife as food, wildlife as a source of income, wildlife conservation, community participation in wildlife management, and wildlife legislation and law enforcement. A conceptual framework for the study is also outlined.

Wildlife as food

In many developing countries including those in sub-Saharan Africa, wildlife is an essential food resource, a source of income for rural people, and an important part of human spiritual and cultural systems (Robinson & Bennett 2000; Mockrin et al 2005). In tropical forest regions, there is often little tradition of domestic livestock management; in regions without strong food production sectors, hunted wildlife can be essential for food security (Mockrin et al 2005), or as a fallback when other sources of food and income are scarce (Bennett, 2002).

With governments of sub-Saharan African countries still struggling to provide the needed protein through domestic animals and from plant sources in the various agricultural programmes, both rural and urban people have no choice but to depend on bushmeat as supplement to these sources. Asibey (1966) claims that most of the large cocoa farms in Brong Ahafo Region, which support the country's economy, could not have been established were it

not for bushmeat, which provided protein for the farmer and his household. According to Asibey and Child (1990) 84 percent of Nigerian communities living near forests obtained their animal protein from bushmeat. The FAO (1989) gave values between 60 and 75 percent respectively for Ghana, Liberia and Botswana for bushmeat consumption. In recent times an attempt has been made to estimate actual consumption of bushmeat in Ghana. In two such studies Dei (1989, 1991) estimated the total amount of bushmeat consumed by an adult per week at a farming village, Akyem Ayirebi, in the Eastern Region as 250g compared to between 100g and 150g for Accra. Ntiamo-Baidu (1998) reports that while most people accept figures about proportions of the population who will eat bushmeat, people also argue about the over-enthusiastic advocacy for the value of bushmeat which seems to suggest that bushmeat is the main source of protein for rural communities. The demand for bushmeat is by no means limited to rural communities. Asibey and Child (1990) state that rapid urbanization has created a spiraling demand for bushmeat in the cities of Africa. Sub-Saharan Africa and particularly in West Africa, this is not a new development as there has been a long tradition of bushmeat trade based on supplies from rural areas to markets in urban areas.

Often people's attention goes unto large wild game animals as the main source of bushmeat, however a lot of animals both vertebrates and invertebrates are sources of bushmeat. Swenson (2005) indicates that the bushmeat trade in Ghana is dominated by the grasscutter, a small rodent. Wild species commonly consumed in tropical forest countries include mammals, birds, reptiles, amphibians, and fish, as well as invertebrates such as termites,

beetles, and snails (Mockrin et al 2005). This has been corroborated by Cowlishaw et al. (2004), Ntiamoa-Baidu (1998) and Asibey and Child (1990).

Ntiamoa-Baidu (1998) puts bushmeat consumers into two groups. The first group, she mentioned are those who completely depend on bushmeat for their protein source either because there are no other sources of protein or they cannot afford alternatives and such people would eat almost all species. The second group of consumers is those who eat bushmeat as a matter of preference or as a luxury and would therefore pay a high price for their preference. This confirms the assertion made by Asibey and Child (1990) that people consider those whose area is endowed with a particular species of animals such as snails as being lucky.

Available evidence suggests that the nutritional content of fresh bushmeat compares favourably with domestic meat. The yield of fresh bushmeat in terms of lean meat per kg of live weight, and in mineral and protein content is as equal as the domestic meat (Asibey and Child 1990; Asibey and Eyeson, 1975). Reul (1979) also indicates that the meat of wild animals has superior fat content than domestic animals. Hladik *et al.* (1987) on his part notes that the preference for bushmeat by consumers even though higher in prices than domestic meat is because of the fatty consistencies of the meat. They argue that the calorie value of bushmeat is as important as the protein it provides.

There are three basic methods of preserving bushmeat. These are smoking, salting and biltong. The method of preservation used depends on the area and the culture of the people as well as the availability of resources. For example, biltong is used when there is availability of sunshine and salt.

Among the methods, the traditional methods of smoking is the most suitable and accepted in most cultures despite its limitations such as high soot content in some cases.

The determining factor influencing wild animal consumption appears to be the adequacy of supply (Ntiamoa-Baidu 1998; 1986). Asibey and Child (1990) state that in all African countries where studies have been conducted, it was abundantly clear that the majority of meat-eating people would eat bushmeat if it were to be available. Martin (1983) reports that studies in Ghana and Nigeria demonstrated this assertion to be true that irrespective of class, income level, educational background, religion or sex of the people, they will consume bushmeat provided it is available. In Gabon, Milius (2005) reports that wealthier families eat more meat including bushmeat and that as wealth increases for people on the lower income brackets, their bushmeat consumption levels also improves. This defeats the belief that bushmeat consumption will decrease with an improvement in the economic situation of a country. The demand for bushmeat has an international link. Milius (2005) and the bushmeat trade reflect the fishing quotas set for the European Union (EU) fleet off the coast of Africa.

Wildlife as a source of income

Direct earnings from wild animal-based small enterprises such as export of live animals for the pet trade are more tangible as statistical data suggest. This trade averages USD 6,600,000 (Azumah 2002). For example, in 2000 alone, Ghana earned more than five billion cedis from exporting reptiles,

mammals, amphibians, scorpions and spiders. The highest revenue earner was the royal python (*Python sebae*) at 2.7 billion cedis.

Bushmeat is by far the most expensive meat in many countries. For example, Asibey (1987) reports that the prices of domestic meat in Ibadan, Nigeria, in 1975 especially mutton and beef were US\$2.80 and \$4.20 per kg respectively as against grasscutter meat which cost as much as \$9.60 per kg and wild hare which cost \$7.20 per kg. Analysis of market prices in Accra, Ghana, revealed that in the early to mid 1980s, bushmeat prices increased eight-fold while prices for domestic meat such as beef increased only six folds (Asibey 1987).

Most of the populations of sub-Saharan African countries are engaged in subsistence agriculture as a major source of employment, which yields minimal economic returns. Therefore activities that generate additional income or reduce expenditure are invaluable, particularly where they enhance the quality of rural life (Asibey and Child 1990). The NTFPs of the forest and especially bushmeat provides such opportunities for inhabitants of communities endowed with the resources. Hunting activities generate considerable income in many parts of Africa (Asibey, 1978a,b, 1987). For example, in the Bendel State of Nigeria, 25 percent of the population's earnings are less than US\$130 per annum, but a grasscutter (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) is sold for US\$7.61. This means a hunter who is able to kill an average of four grasscutters per month could earn much higher income (Martin, 1983). Asibey (1987) made similar findings in Ghana when he reported that in January 1987 the official minimum daily wage was 90 cedis, at the same time a grasscutter sold for a minimum of 200 cedis in the rural

areas, and from 700 to 3400 cedis in Accra. Ntiamoa-Baidu (1998) gave the average income earnings of the hunter per week as being negative figures (where the hunter actually spent money on hunting inputs without a catch) to ₵500,000.00 when there was a catch. The net profit from hunting expedition depends on the location of the hunter. While the national average income earning of the hunter is ₵46,420, it ranges between a meager ₵2,500 in the savannah zone to a high ₵101,400 in the transition zone (Ntiamoa-Baidu 1998). Asibey's (1978b) assertion that farmers who also practice hunting more than doubled their agricultural income by selling bushmeat is therefore relevant. For many people in the rural areas income from hunting is an essential part of their subsistence economy.

The high demand for bushmeat and its cost compared to other sources of protein has created a situation where the hunter delights in selling his catch than eat it (Asibey and Child 1990). The income derived from hunting is often spent on cheaper protein (usually poorly preserved fish) with the savings used to meet other expenses (Asibey, 1974b, 1978a,b). Ntiamoa-Baidu (1998) gave these percentage distributions for the hunters catch, 53.7% of the animals killed were sold, and 14.3% were given as gifts, while 33.8% were eaten. The report indicates a relatively higher percentage of meat being eaten and the explanation is that most of the species killed were rodents and they are the species which the hunter eats. When the kill was converted to estimated weights it was found out that as much as 82.2% was sold while a mere 13.7% was eaten. This practice has the potential to affect the diet of the hunter and his family adversely and can threaten their food security in terms of quality and nutritional status of diet.

Bushmeat harvesting and trading has created other industries such as the sale of firearms and ammunition. Ntiamoa-Baidu (1998) mentions that the hunter incurs both capital and recurrent cost in the hunting business. The main capital cost is the acquisition of a gun. Most of the guns in use today were acquired between 1970 and 1997 and prices quoted ranged from ¢700 to ¢400,000. The recurrent cost of the hunter was mainly hunting accessories such as torchlight, batteries, ammunition, carbide, matches and in some cases transportation to hunting sites and to markets. Of these items three of them: ammunition, batteries and carbide constitute about 80% of the total recurrent cost of the hunter. The average hunting cost per week in towns was about ¢9,000 and in a city it was ¢11,400 (Ntiamoa-Baidu 1998). Estimates for deer, elk and bighorn sheep hunting has a reasonable economic impact on total personal income per hunter day (or per trip day or hunter for bighorn sheep hunting).

Figure 1: Bushmeat trade actors and levels of interactions, Ghana.

Source: Cowlshaw et al 2004: 2.

There are well-established chains, from the hunter through go-betweens/processors, transporters, to retailers in the cities. Cowlshaw et al (2004) diagrammatically depicts the actors of the bushmeat harvesting and trading and their level of interaction in Ghana (Fig. 1).

The size of the arrow is a proportion of the weight in kilograms of bushmeat trade between the various actors. There are five main participants: farmer hunters, commercial hunters, wholesalers, market traders and chopbars operators (traditional restaurants). According to Cowlshaw et al (2004) all hunters are men, while all other actors are women. Hunters live and work in the rural areas and capture their prey using unapproved methods such as wire snares, gin traps and an approved method of gunshot. Commercial hunters

depend entirely on bushmeat for their livelihood, whereas farmer hunters sell bushmeat to supplement their income from agricultural produce. The women traders – wholesalers, market traders and chopbar operators –live and work in the cities and towns. Wholesalers work from home where they buy their wares in bulk from the hunters and sell to the retailers. Market traders operate from stalls in the market, whereas chopbars are scattered across the major towns and cities in Ghana. Chopbars vary in size, while some are small; others are extremely large and require several staff to run. The assistants at the chopbars who operate as cooks, waitresses and cleaners are also invariably women. The main clientele for market traders are women, whereas chopbars are patronised by men (Cowlshaw et al 2004).

Bushmeat consumption is not limited to developing countries alone but also it is an item of international trade. However, notwithstanding the considerable amount of bushmeat production in Africa, no country stands out as an exporter (Asibey and Child 1990). This could be attributed in part to the stringent standards demanded by the principal importers. Notable importers of bushmeat are the Federal Republic of Germany and France. Milius (2005) also reports of a market in a warehouse in New York, where a dozen or so vendors displayed tables stacked with smoked meat priced from \$5 to \$8 per pound, which probably originated from Ghana. Most countries of the region (except Ghana) still give no systematic consideration to bushmeat consumption or trade at national levels of planning, finance and development (Asibey and Child 1990) and the limited information collected remains unpublished. This is a serious omission, with undesirable consequences for those whose survival is closely linked to wild animals, as a source of food and income as well as for

cultural consideration. It also affects efforts to conserve and manage wildlife resources.

Wildlife conservation

The ecosystems produce food, clean water, manage disease and regulate the climate. Over the last half-century, however, people have changed ecosystems more than at any other period in the history of the earth. Changes to ecosystems caused by human activities have caused three major problems: sixty percent of ecosystem services are being degraded or used unsustainably; ecosystem changes have become more unpredictable, leading to dramatic events such as regional climate change; and the negative impacts of ecosystem degradation are mostly felt by poor people, meaning it contributes to increasing global inequality (Reid et al 2005). The changes to the ecosystem over the last fifty years have been caused by the following factors:

- Increasing human demands for food, water and fuel which have led to a large and permanent loss in biodiversity;
- Unsustainable natural resources exploitation;
- Ecosystem degradation;
- Managing ecosystem services is difficult because changes are slow and complex and this often eludes policy makers and;
- Different people receive and suffer the costs and benefits of changing ecosystem management in different places.

The degradation of ecosystem services is a major barrier to achieving the Millennium Development Goals (Reid et al 2005). To arrest the degradation in the ecosystem, positive future scenarios would require significant investments in environmentally protective technologies, as well as investments in public goods (particularly education and health) and poverty reduction. The following measures have been suggested:

- Methods of ecosystem management must be flexible so that they can adapt to future ecosystem changes.
- Development planning must integrate ecosystem management with other sectors. Including better coordination between environmental agreements and international economic and social agreements.
- Governments and private sector organizations must be more open about the environmental impacts of their activities.
- Powerful governments must be prepared to eliminate subsidies that promote over use of ecosystem services. At the same time, they must develop financial incentives to ensure payment for ecosystem services.

Most countries are not yet adopting the right targets and indicators to assess whether they are achieving sound, equitable natural resources management for poverty reduction (Hazlewood and Tunstall 2005). Many countries especially those in sub-Saharan Africa lack the data or the resources to adequately monitor progress in environmental sustainability. In some instances, a lack of reporting suggests that countries are not making sufficient investments in environmental resources or environmental governance (Hazlewood and Tunstall 2005). However, farmers and policy makers need information on a range of factors (including soils, crops, livestock breeds and wildlife populations) at the scale of their village or local community to the national level in order to manage these resources sustainably.

In recent years, concern has been growing about the unsustainable levels of wildlife hunting, especially in tropical forests (Robinson & Bennett, 2000; Mockrin et al 2005). According to Crookes and Milner-Gulland (2006) at least 17 species that are hunted for bushmeat in West Africa, many of which

are endemic to the region, are on the IUCN red list of threatened species, and one primate, Miss Waldron's colobus (*Piliocolobus badius waldronae*), was once believed to be extinct although new evidence suggests that a small number may be living in the southeastern corner of La Cote d'Ivoire. Growing human populations, the introduction of modern hunting techniques, increased access to diminishing areas of forests, and increasing commercialization of hunting have all increased pressure on wildlife populations (Robinson & Bennett, 2000; Mockrin et al, 2005). Recent estimates of annual bushmeat harvest of 23,500 tonnes in the Malaysian state of Sarawak, 67,000 to 164,000 tonnes in the Brazilian Amazon, and one million tonnes in Central Africa underpins the suspicion that current rates of bushmeat harvesting are not sustainable. This is causing population declines and local extinctions of many species across the world's tropical forests (Bennett & Robinson, 2000), leading to the question of whether food security for tropical forest people is being compromised by the decline in the wildlife resource.

Theoretical calculations for Central Africa Bushmeat project predicted that, at present harvest rates, the protein supply from bushmeat would drop by 81 percent over the next 50 years (Mockrin et al, 2005). If the availability of bushmeat is not increased, rural consumption may decline, as the rate of exploitation and intensity of hunting to supply urban markets are increased by demand (Asibey and Child, 1990). The protein supply situation in sub-Saharan Africa needs to be improved in order not to compound the already precarious malnutrition situation in most countries where domestic animal husbandry and plant sources are unable to meet protein needs of the people. The socio-

economic cost of this situation if not checked, could be dangerous to the rural communities.

Wildlife conservation and management efforts have been developed from concern over the severe depletion and in some cases near or complete extinction of selected large game species such as the lion, elephant and rhino. These large species represent in most cases significant potential sources of national income through tourism and trophy hunting. The most common approach to arrest the continuous threat to wildlife species existence has been the application of stringent laws designed to prevent all exploitation of wildlife within protected areas, and to restrict utilization severely throughout the country (Asibey and Child, 1990). Some restrictions outside protected areas in Ghana include regulating hunting methods and through a license regime. Where animals and their habitat are in danger, this approach is often the only practical first step available toward long-term sustained conservation and management (Asibey and Child, 1990).

For a long term approach there are various options. The simplest and often the most effective approach is to protect existing populations (Asibey and Child, 1990). Where viable populations no longer remain, suitable parts of the former range of a species may be selected for reintroduction. There is evidence that introduced species can multiply to economically exploitable levels (Teer, 1971). The technology is available but funding is a constraint. Attractive returns that have been demonstrated need to be further consolidated and better communicated to potential investors. Milius (2005) suggests that to tackle the over hunting of wildlife, a mix of approaches should be instituted. Both forest and urban people need alternative food and income sources to

meet basic needs in tough times. The underpaid workers in camps that push into pristine forests need ways to feed themselves without emptying the landscape of animals. Also, governments need help to limit the sale of bushmeat hunting and trade. During past decades, some conservationists argued that a good programme to protect the environment would improve the lot of local people (Milius, 2005). From afar, the idea looks beautifully logical: reduce poverty in tropical forests, and forest dwellers will have access to food without hunting bushmeat.

Community participation in wildlife management

Wildlife conservation based on stringent laws application and project initiatives, which do not take into consideration the needs of the local communities, are bound to fail. Asibey and Child (1990) mentions that there is clear evidence that attempts to protect or re-establish wildlife resources that ignore the local level considerations (socio-economic and culture) are doomed to fail as preservation laws are flouted with impunity. In such circumstances where the survival of the people depends on wild animals, which provide food and cash, the temptation to break the preservation laws is great. According to Asibey and Child (1990) another problem which makes it difficult to obey preservation laws is that the officers who should enforce the law are often poorly paid and therefore may be tempted to turn a blind eye to offenders. In some cases they aid rich illegal exploiters to perpetuate the illegality. One other factor is also inadequate staffing in most protected areas as this negatively affects supervision. According to Jachman (2007) in Ghana,

budgetary allocations for protected area management have been consistently low and lack of funds obviously affects monitoring operations.

Protected area (PA) and wildlife management have now moved with time and management has shifted gradually from application of stringent laws to collaborative management with local authorities and even devolving of wildlife rights to the local communities in some countries. There is no doubt that if a wildlife management programme is to be effective in the long term, it must be based on the active involvement and participation of local people.

Variants of such community involvement in wildlife management have been implemented in Zimbabwe, Mozambique and in Ghana. The Community Forestry and Wildlife Management (CFWM) is a strategy that the government of Mozambique is embarking on to promote the sustainable use and conservation of wildlife resources (Mansur and Zacharias, 2003). Under this programme, which was adopted from the 1997 Forests and Wildlife policy of Mozambique, local communities are recognized as legal entities responsible for the use and conservation of forests and wildlife resources under their area of influence. According to Mansur and Zacharias (2003) this approach has been attractive to the local people, government officials and the donor community and up to that time sixty- one (61) community-based natural resources management (CBNRM) have been established in ten provinces in Mozambique. They mention the challenge to effective implementation of the programme to be lack of trained personnel to manage these areas as well as lack of instituted legal and regulatory frameworks for serious community forestry take off.

In Ghana the Wildlife Division is implementing the establishment of Community Resource Management Areas (CREMAs). The development of CREMAs in Ghana applies the same principles used elsewhere to Ghanaian conditions. The CREMA concept is based on the establishment of areas where wildlife management is incorporated into existing land use. The concept is based on the “community” as the management unit but due to the diversity of circumstance, the definition of community will be determined in each case by the people themselves. The Community Resource Management Areas (CREMA) in Ghana emanates from the 1994 Forest and Wildlife Policy, which states among other things in its guiding principle is the rights of local people to have access to natural resources for maintaining a basic standard of living and their concomitant responsibility to ensure the suitable use of such resources. In view of the importance of local people in pursuing these principles, the Government of Ghana proposes to place particular emphasis on the concept of participatory management and protection of forest and wildlife resources and will seek to develop appropriate strategies, modalities and programmes in consultation with relevant agencies, rural communities and individuals. The CREMA approach therefore thrives on these guiding principles adopted from Living Earth Foundation (2007).

- Effective management of wildlife is best achieved by giving it a focused value.
- Those who live with and bear the cost of wildlife must be the primary beneficiaries of its management.
- The control of access and benefit from wildlife whether by the individual or collectively must be determined by those who live with the resource

- Wildlife should be recognized in its own right as an integral and viable component of national land use policy.
- Wildlife is a unique natural resource offering various opportunities for sustainable rural development and economic utilization.
- To create the incentive for sustainable wildlife management at community level the authority to manage and benefit from wildlife must be devolved to an appropriate representative community institution.
- The role of traditional authorities, traditional knowledge, and other cultural aspects in wildlife management be recognized and encouraged in national strategies and wildlife management techniques.

According to the Living Earth Foundation (2007) there are some challenges to the CREMA approach in managing wildlife resources in Ghana.

These are:

- Failure to correctly identify the local decision making structures could result in a powerless CREMA
- Communities that are deeply divided over other issues may not be able to develop sufficient consensus to form a CREMA
- The CREMA approach is a process and especially in the early stages requires time, technical support and funding
- Inadequate funds to support the process leading to establishment of the CREMA.
- Legitimization of unsustainable hunting of wildlife.
- Single/few individuals may hijack CREMA.

To date one such CREMA has been established in the Western Region and has been issued a certificate near Ankasa National Park by the Wildlife Division.

A number of other areas are now awaiting approval from the Wildlife Division.

The integration of wildlife into land use system whereby wildlife, crops, livestock co-exist is another form of community involvement in wildlife management in outside protected areas. Both wild and domestic animals convert vegetable matter into valuable meat; however, until recently wild animals have been exterminated intentionally to allow exclusive use of rangelands by domestic stock (Asibey and Child 1990). This practice of exclusive use of rangelands by livestock to the detriment of wildlife might have come up due to limited knowledge, fear of reduction in productivity as a result of competition between wild and domestic animals. There is a belief too that wild animals transfer diseases to domestic animals. In the past, the general view among both conservationists and local populations has been that wildlife conservation and animal husbandry are incompatible forms of land use and should be kept apart (Boyd et al, 1999). However, competition and conflicts over land use and access to water have intensified as human and animal populations' pressure on rangelands and international concern for the conservation of biological diversity have increased. Boyd et al (1999) advocate for new techniques and opportunities to address these conflicts and concerns in order to derive from more dynamic concepts of rangeland ecology and changes in conservation philosophies to incorporate benefits to local people. However, the impacts of efforts to integrate conservation and development are difficult to appraise or evaluate. Asibey and Child (1990) challenge these concerns of livestock farmers by indicating that the elimination of wild animals does not necessarily lead to maximum utilization

of vegetation on rangelands as domestic animals are selective in their feeding and not all plants on the range are utilized. A variety of compatible animals have been managed together in South Africa and they do not compete for food resources. Asibey and Asare (1978) mention possible suitable mix of domestic and wild animal species as domestic cattle and kudu as well as impala and hartebeest. There are advantages associated in combining livestock and wild animals on a rangeland such as the plants being consumed by the wild animals, would otherwise have to be controlled manually or chemically. It is therefore more economical to combine livestock with wild animals on rangelands to maximize the use of vegetation and avoid the need for weed control. The additional revenue that can be derived from wild animals through sport hunting and recreation should also be borne in mind as some of the advantages in keeping wild animals and livestock.

Foresters normally regard NTFPs including bushmeat as minor products from the forest and therefore not much attention is given to wildlife in forest reserves. Wild animals are one of the most important direct contributors to forests regeneration as well as the well being of local people (Asibey and Child, 1990). Some forest management practices and techniques tend to increase wildlife numbers while others cause wildlife population to decline. For example Prins and Reitsma (1989) as in Asibey and Child (1990) mention selective timber extraction, which enhances vegetation growth and favours increases in the populations of many forest animals. In contrast, indiscriminate felling of trees decrease wildlife numbers as habitat decreases and inaccessible places open up leading to increases in hunting. Based upon

this Asibey and Child (1990) recommend hunting rights for local people to hunt in exchange for assistance in reforestation efforts in degraded forest.

Traditionally, wildlife plays an important role in the life of many sub-Saharan Africans and wildlife was managed through a system of traditional beliefs culminating in setting up sacred groves, taboos and festivals. There are more than two thousand sacred groves guarded and respected by the local people in Ghana (Pleydell, 2005; Wildlife Development Plan, 1998). Colonization and modernization has gradually eroded these belief systems and hitherto sacred animals are eaten. This phenomenon has led to another form of community- government collaborative management of wildlife resources. The Buaben-Fiema Monkey Sanctuary in the Brong Ahafo Region is one such collaborative management area. The area has two species of monkeys- Mona Monkey (*Cercopithecus mona*) and Pied Colobus Monkey (*Colobus polycomos*), which are believed to be the children of the gods of the two communities and are therefore sacred. In more recent years the traditional taboos have become weaker, but the community participated in the creation of the local District Assembly bylaw to maintain protection for the monkey species and the Wildlife Division helps in this respect (Pleydell, 2005). This initiative has been replicated in Tafi-Atome monkey sanctuary, Wli waterfall and Agumatsa monkey Sanctuary all in the Volta Region of Ghana. These initiatives have generated considerable tourist attraction to the sites and funds generated are being used for community development.

Wildlife legislation and law enforcement

Law enforcement is paramount in maintaining viable populations of wildlife (Jachman, 2007; Pleydell, 2005) but in practice it is not possible to have on the spot policing across the whole country. Such is the magnitude of the task of monitoring and enforcing wildlife legislation. Many people including law enforcement agencies are not aware of the laws regulating hunting and those who are aware of the laws recognize the weakness of the system for enforcement and openly flout the laws (Ntiamoa-Baidu, 1998). As Asibey and Child (1990) have put it, legislation is a major constraint to the utilization of wild animals for food in subsistence economies, as it is designed to protect endangered species and regulate trophy hunting. Most of the laws designed in sub-Saharan African countries are mimics of what is perceived in Europe and thus, such concepts as game animals, hunting seasons, bag limits, trophies, hunting reserves and royal game, have been freely adopted (Asibey and Child 1990). The applicability of these adopted laws has not taken into consideration the biological validity of the animals under tropical conditions.

Ghana's wildlife resources are mainly managed through a system of protected areas (seventeen inland conservation areas, a zoo and five coastal wetland-Ramsar sites), a closed season (from 1st August to 1st December every year in which no species may be hunted and traded on the market with the exception of grasscutters –*Thryonomys swinderianus*) and through restrictions on species that may be hunted. Besides, hunters are required to be in possession of a game license and a game and trophy export permit for removal of game from the country. Other restrictions on hunting include prohibitions of hunting methods such as the use of gin traps and hunting in groups.

The effect of such legislation is that traditional utilization is ignored or defined as poaching and the technologies used declared unlawful methods of hunting (Asibey and Child, 1990). According to Akumsi (2003), a gun license is required as a prerequisite to acquiring hunting permits in the Cameroon; however local manufactured guns are widely used by hunters and these guns are not recognized by the administration and therefore cannot be issued with gun licenses. The local hunters are therefore left with the only option of illegal hunting, using local guns that they can easily purchase. Again, possession, disposal and commercialization of wild animal meat or other products without a license are illegal. It is argued that strict protected areas management interventions (command and control methods) are most likely to promote conservation; however these come at a high livelihood and enforcement cost, since voluntary compliance is expected to be low (Crookes and Milner-Gulland 2006). Their assertion is based on the belief that supply restrictions are likely to provide a lower level of conservation effectiveness even though this would depend on the type of restriction introduced.

According to Asibey and Child (1990) when the focus of restriction is on endangered and trophy species, as in national wildlife legislations in many developing countries, the efforts have had a negative effect on the management of species that do not fall into these categories. The institution of state ownership of wildlife, centrally imposed licenses and restrictions on the sale of products alienates and prevent landholders from considering wildlife management as a potentially profitable land use option. Thus, there are no incentives to conserve wildlife as a land use system option.

Bushmeat trade does not appear to be properly regulated based on any rules or regulations to ensure the wholesomeness of the meat (Ntiamo-Baidu 1998). It is not surprising therefore for Mensah (2003) to report in the Daily Guide Newspaper that bushmeat in Ghana is sometimes killed by dangerous chemicals. In Ghana bushmeat is sold to unsuspecting consumers from all locations including the roadside, homes and in unclean markets where carcasses are displayed on the ground- a mark of unregulated market.

The wildlife estate was established to protect representative samples of Ghana's various ecological communities, and currently comprises 17 protected areas (two of which remain to be gazetted). Together they form 13,048km² or 5.5% of the country's land area, and include seven National Parks, five Resources Reserves, and four Wildlife Sanctuaries and one Strict Nature Reserve (Pleydell, 2005; Wildlife Development Plan 1998). These protected areas are the primary focus of the Wildlife Division management programmes and according to the Wildlife Development Plan Document (1998) about 90% of the division's staff members are deployed in the field to protect and manage them. Management of the four categories of protected areas are similar even though the set up objectives differ because resources protection and law enforcement remain the core activities in the protected areas. The Wildlife Division wants to manage other wildlife estates in the forest reserves endowed with sufficient wildlife resources designed as Globally Significant Biodiversity Areas (GSBAs).

A Senior Wildlife Officer, frequently assisted by one or more Assistant Wildlife Officers and often a Protection Officer in charge of law enforcement, manages protected areas in Ghana (Jachman, 2007). Wildlife Rangers make up

the next hierarchy below this level. The Rangers are in charge of a particular area called a range where patrols emanate. The ranges are made up of satellite patrol camps manned by a minimum of four field patrol staff. Patrol staff members are of varying ranks, with the most senior patrol staff acting as camp or patrol leader. It is a generally accepted practice to have a striking force normally called anti-poaching team in protected areas.

Jachman (2007) states that considering the financial constraints in protected area management in Africa there is the need for cheap, sustainable and standardized methods to collect patrol information. Such a system should aim at monitoring feedback to make law enforcement more effective and cost efficient, while at the same time improving performance of the law enforcement programmes in protected areas.

Conceptual framework for study

The conceptual framework, used for the study is adopted from Crookes and Milner-Gulland (2006). The framework was used in evaluating the impact of policy interventions on the supply chain of bushmeat in some markets in Ghana by the authors. Many approaches to reducing hunting pressure have been suggested, all of which impact on users to some extent. However, there has been little rigorous analysis of how these impacts are distributed. This particular framework (figure 2) discusses the key determinants of impact distribution, including who is targeted, who implements the policies, ability and willingness to comply with enforcement measures, and ecosystem characteristics. The framework analyzes the effects of policy tools on hunter and market behaviour.

Policy is defined in the broad sense, to include interventions at a national, regional and local (community) level (Crookes and Milner-Gulland, 2006). A decision tree approach is adopted for measuring the impact of policies as can be seen in figure 2. There are a number of other tools, which may be utilized including conservation monitoring and evaluation approaches (Salafsky & Margoluis, 2003; Crookes and Milner-Gulland, 2005).

An overall evaluation of the effects of particular policies on bushmeat hunting behaviour is complex, since it presupposes an evaluation framework and criteria (Crookes and Milner-Gulland, 2006). Furthermore, a detailed evaluation of policy effects requires context-specific information, which should involve an integrated assessments taking into account environmental, economic and social aspects. Since trade in bushmeat may occur in various contexts: at a community level, it involves hunting for subsistence and sale to markets. At the market level, trade flows occur between various actors, including traders, butchers, restaurateurs or chop bar owners, and final consumers (Mendelson et al. 2003; Cowlshaw et al 2004). Cognisance should also be taken of the greater socio-political context, since other policy decisions may also affect bushmeat consumption and trade (for example, timber logging or agriculture and fishing rights policies). A broad range of criteria may be used to assess policy impacts of measures for improving the sustainability of the bushmeat trade. The focus would be the nature of the policy, the target groups and the implementers of the policy. The framework would look at the subsequent effect on the flow of bushmeat along the supply chain.

The most common types of policy are those whose primary aim is to target bushmeat supply, either directly or indirectly through the market and such policies include protected areas management, and supply side restrictions such as gear, species and seasonal restrictions on hunting. A second category of policy is that which mitigates the effects of a reduction in bushmeat supply and examples include providing alternative sources of protein and promoting alternative income sources. Based on the overall market structure of the bushmeat trade in Ghana, it is possible to identify at least four groups of people who are likely to be affected by policy interventions in the bushmeat sector: hunters, intermediaries (including restaurants, traders and butchers), subsistence consumers (mainly in rural areas) and commercial consumers (mainly in peri-urban or urban areas). For example, policies focused on hunters could be community based or implemented in a top down manner by authorities. Furthermore, whilst supply side policies are more likely to be implemented by wildlife authorities, monetary and fiscal authorities will probably undertake market-based interventions, whilst community based interventions may be facilitated by non-governmental organizations. Often, these agents are active at different levels of intervention with different priorities.

Examples of such policies include spatial management policies which look at the establishment and enforcement of protected areas, and management through the use of buffer zones, sources and sinks and the establishment of core areas of supply. Examples of supply side measures include equipment (gear) restrictions, restrictions on the species that may be hunted, quotas on the numbers of individuals that may be hunted, seasonal hunting policies, and

quotas on the number of hunters allowed to operate in a particular areas (for example through privatization of the resource). An example for such a policy includes, protected area policies which are implemented on an ecosystem-level, and the market bans are market level. Many policies (such as supply side measures) may be more effective when implemented at the community level. The Wildlife Division of Ghana as a policy intervention carry out conservation education, regulate hunting seasons and species to be hunted. The Division is also tasked to manage protected areas which have been created purposely to contain representative samples of animal species of the country. Figure 2 shows a number of policy interventions and executing agencies and possible outcomes.

Figure 2: A conceptual framework for evaluating wildlife hunting and trading restrictions.

Source: Crookes and Milner-Gulland, 2006

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The survey was conducted in five markets around the Digya National Park. The markets are Atebubu, Amanten, Tato and Kajaji in the Brong Ahafo Region. The other market is the Maame Krobo market in the Afram Plains of the Eastern Region. Many people from this country and even beyond come to these markets for trading in bushmeat and other wares making it appropriate for the study.

Two groups were targeted for data on bushmeat harvested from different locations and sold in these markets. The two groups are the hunters (commercial and farmer hunters) and bushmeat traders (wholesalers, retailers and chopbar operators). Information on hunting methods, species killed, level of awareness of wildlife hunting and trading regulations and also operators' perception of the current license regimes was collected. Target group demographic data such as age, sex and how long they have been in the bushmeat hunting and trading business were collected for analysis. Desktop study was conducted to collect data on the bushmeat license issued for a ten-year period (1998-2007) at the Digya National Park. Data on illegal hunters arrested for the period were also collected.

Since the bushmeat business could be illegal and therefore would be difficult in getting respondents a snowballing sampling technique was used

(Swenson 2005). Also to prevent the prediction of operators to know the possible dates and days the team would visit each market, a simple random sampling of the market days of the selected markets was carried out through the lottery method.

To ensure a fair representation, all groups of people who were identified in relation to the bushmeat trade and hunting in each of the markets and the towns were interviewed. The methods used to collect the data were in-depth interviews, focus group discussions and direct observations of species killed. For fresh animals killed, data were collected on the sex, reproductive condition and the capture method. Five teams of three were trained for each of the markets to collect information on the bushmeat. After the training, the interview instrument was tested to iron out all potential difficulties. The researcher accompanied each of the teams in rotation with time to ensure uniformity. Each team visited each market six times, three times in the closed season and three times in the open season. The whole study lasted for eight months that is from 1st August to 1st December for the closed season and from 1st January to 1st May. These periods coincide with the major hunting season in the study area. Data were also analyzed using the statistical programme for scientific solutions (SPSS) and Excel software programmes for descriptive statistics.

Sampling technique

Two sampling techniques were used in getting respondents for the study. These were snowballing technique for sampling hunters and traders and a simple random sampling procedure for sampling dates to visit the five

markets. The snowballing technique was first to identify a key informant, in this case the chief hunter and the market queen responsible for bushmeat harvesting and trading in each market/town. The team explained their mission to them and assured them that the exercise is for academic purposes since anything contrary would have suggested a possible arrest of offenders leading to suppression of information. During the period of interview no arrest of respondents was made but rather the opportunity was used to educate respondents who had killed prohibited species and the use of unauthorized methods. The key informant was interviewed first and after that the team requested for the locations of people who are into the bushmeat business (hunters and traders) for them also to be interviewed. Anybody interviewed was not interviewed again during a subsequent visit to the market but rather direct observation of species killed was carried out on their wares on each visit. However an operator missed on the previous visit would be interviewed in the subsequent one.

In order to get maximum co-operation from operators in the bushmeat industry, visits to the markets were made unpredictably so as to get the actual information on the ground. It is believed that when operators get to know the days of visit they might cover up any wrong doing by parading only permitted hunted species while illegal operators would not turn up. To avoid this, a simple random method using the lottery procedure was used to select market days to be visited. Table 1 shows the towns and their market days of the week.

Table 1: Towns and their market days

Town	Market day of the week
Maame Krobo	Monday
Atebubu	Tuesday
Tato	Wednesday
Kajaji	Thursday
Amanten	Friday

Source: Field survey, 2007

To get a date to visit each market, for example Maame Krobo, all Mondays in a particular month was written into a basket and shuffled, from which a day was selected and that would be the day the Maame Krobo market was visited in that month. This was repeated for all other markets according to their market days. Hunting season period for the study area normally begins in September where farming activities have been completed in the year and ends in April where farming activity is starting. Based on this, visits to the markets for the closed season were September, October and November while the open season visits were in January, February and March. The selection for one market day for a town per month was done to avoid two possible consecutive visits to a market within the same month. This was also to avoid respondents' fatigue. Each of the sixth visits to the markets for the two seasons was used to conduct a Focus Group Discussion (FGD). By this visit, the teams had identified the key members in the bushmeat industries in each of the location.

In-depth interviews

The in-depth interviews were conducted in the local languages of the people around the Digya National Park. The languages considered were Twi and Ewe languages. In situations where the respondents could speak the English language, interviews were conducted in English. The team composition for the survey was based on the fluency of team members in these languages. Team members were trained to translate the questionnaire into these languages. The in-depth interview made it possible for respondents to express themselves freely and also gave interviewers the chance to probe more for answers. Five such interviews were conducted in each market for the study period but the sixth visit was used for a focus group discussion. No one in a location was interviewed twice during the study period but could be a participant during the focus group discussion. Since a snowballing sampling method was employed all people who are engaged in the hunting and bushmeat trade who could be identified were interviewed to have a fair representation of operators in the business. The team would arrive early in the morning possibly 6:00 am and they stayed till most traders had left the market so that they would not miss any potential respondents because experience has shown that hunters arrived early in the markets to sell their wares. Team members conducted visits to chopbars and homes of wholesalers in the towns to conduct interviews and also to have direct observations. The data collected included sex, age, how long he/she has been in the business, hunting methods and the level of awareness of the hunting laws. Respondents' level of awareness was assessed based on their level of knowledge about the hunting regulations. Also respondents were asked for their hunting and trading license.

Focus group discussion (FGD)

A focus group discussion was carried out at each of the five selected markets. The FGD, which was conducted during the sixth visit to each of the location, comprised key members of the bushmeat industry in each of the selected markets. Selected participants were hunters and traders at different levels of operation. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select twelve participants to each market location. The team to each location identified key operators and those who were cooperative in the last five visits were selected to be participants. A discussion guide was designed to meet the objectives of the study. The focus group discussion complemented the data gathered during the in-depth interviews.

Direct observation

A direct observation of species killed on each visit was carried out in all the five locations. This was necessary in order to achieve the objective of evaluating the effectiveness of the current closed season period. Data collected covered the type of species hunted. For fresh animals data on sex and capture method were observed (gunshot wounds, trap marks, cutlass wounds and for poisoned meat no marks would be visible). The reproductive condition of the females would be assessed from teat milk and visible signs of pregnancy (Ntiamoah-Baidu, 1998).

Desktop data collection

Secondary data for hunting and bushmeat trading license issued by the Digya National Park were also collected and analyzed to obtain periods of

increases or otherwise in hunting and trading in bushmeat. This data covered a ten-year period from 1998 to 2007. Also illegal hunters arrested and prosecuted in the law courts by the Digya National Park for the period would be analyzed. Information such as the offence committed, where offender was arrested and the punishment meted to the culprits was taken for analysis.

Data analysis

The data collected were cleaned and coded for presentation. The cleaning was to reduce possible errors and data gaps received from respondents due to differences in the teams approach from the different locations. Cleaning of data is necessary since it is possible for the different teams to have unrecorded some responses or might have forgotten to ask some questions. All data collected from the five markets were treated separately to facilitate easy identification, editing and for coding. The two hunting periods' data for each location was also separated for easy comparison between seasons and also among locations. The data were then combined for analysis. Frequency distribution tables and graphs were constructed to give a pictorial presentation of the data collected.

CHAPTER FOUR

BUSHMEAT HUNTING AND TRADE: THE ISSUES

Introduction

The chapter analyzes the data collected on bushmeat hunting and trading in markets around the Digya National Park. The analysis procedure seeks to provide answers to the research questions and the objectives set out for the study. It begins with respondents' characteristics and moves on to such as species traded at the markets during the study period, hunting seasons and the traded species, and traders' awareness on hunting methods as against the wildlife hunting regulations and restrictions. Traders' awareness of the wildlife regulations as they affect their trade is also analyzed. Also hunters' catch, hunting methods, awareness on the regulations and restrictions affecting their operations is also analyzed.

The chapter also presents findings on the species which were observed either as pregnant or lactating and the periods of those observations. Desktop study findings of the Digya National Park on game license issued, illegal hunters arrested and prosecuted together with revenue generated from confiscated bushmeat is also presented.

Traders' demography and locations

The study was designed to research into the bushmeat trade and hunting in five markets around the Digya National Park and compared the activities of

traders and hunters to the hunting regulations of Ghana. The section presents the characteristics of the traders interviewed. It looks at the sex, age, occupation and educational background of traders.

The design aimed at interviewing hunters and traders at the market places, however field conditions showed that not all the operators conduct their trade at the market places especially hunters, and therefore interviews were also conducted in hunters' and traders' home. Table 2 shows the location of traders and the number interviewed.

Table 2: Traders frequency and locations

Location	Male	Female	Frequency	Percent
Atebubu	31	24	55	24.2
Maame Krobo	37	75	112	49.3
Tato	4	9	13	5.7
Kajaji	11	18	29	12.8
Amantin	7	11	18	8.0
Total	90	137	227	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

A total of 227 traders were interviewed in the five markets for the eight-month study period. Maame Krobo had the highest percentage points of traders interviewed (49.3%) while Tato had the least identified traders (5.7%). The number of bushmeat traders is a general reflection of total market patronage of other goods as well as availability of bushmeat for purchase. Other satellite markets such as Kyeamkrom and Kwame Danso affect the Tato market patronage. For example, the Kwame Danso market is also held on

Wednesday, the same day that the Tato market is held. Therefore, some hunters may prefer selling their wares at the Kwame Danso and Kyeamekrom which are situated on the main road. However, the study chose the Tato market over these two markets because it is a major fishing centre which leads to attraction of hunters to sell their wares in the market.

Sex of respondents

It was necessary to look at the gender of traders in the market place since women in Ghana have generally dominated trading into foodstuff. This was also important to determine if gender has any effect on how the wildlife regulation is respected.

Of the respondents, 39.6% were males while 60.4% were females (Table 3). The male percentage of 39.6% is an interesting phenomenon in a foodstuff trade which should have been completely dominated by females under normal conditions. This is contrary to Cowlshaw et al (2004) findings in Takoradi where while all hunters were men, all other actors in the bushmeat trade were women. The males are however not into retailing; they send their wares to market women who sell the meat in whole or in pieces. When the males were asked as to why they are engaged in the trade apart from being an employment source, the response was that it is also a difficult trade which needs the practitioners to be strong. The trade sometimes requires operators to walk long distances to hunters' hamlets or ride bicycles before they can get wares to buy. This obviously put the female traders at a disadvantage. Actually at Atebubu, one of the study centres, of the 55 traders interviewed, males dominated the market with 56.4%.

Table 3: Sex of respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	90	39.6
Female	137	60.4
Total	227	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

The average age of respondents was 45 years (range 19 to 68 years). Length of trading in bushmeat experience ranged from two months to thirty years with a mean trading experience of five years. The educational level of traders ranged from a low level of having not attended school before to the highest level of secondary education.

Traders classification on fulltime/part-time bases

Most traders (76.6%) were found to be part-time traders. The part-time traders are engaged in other occupations such as trading in foodstuffs as well as trading in bushmeat. Most female part-time traders were engaged in selling other foodstuffs but will trade in bushmeat anytime they had some. Of the 174 traders, 40.8% were males. The male part-time traders only join the trade during the opened season which starts from December and end in late April every year. This period is characterized with high levels of bushmeat production because of the use of bushfires in hunting. During the closed season and the start of the farming season, most male part-time traders stop trading in bushmeat to engage in other ventures such as farming and trading in other stuffs. Table 4 shows the classification of traders according to whether being part-time or full time.

Table 4: Trader classification

Classification	Frequency	Percent
Full time	53	23.3
Part-time	174	76.7
Total	227	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

Fulltime traders are those traders whose sole trading activity is in bushmeat. Fifty three of such traders were identified and were interviewed during the study. Of the 53 fulltime traders, 35.8% were males with the highest male traders occurring at Maame Krobo with 12 males. One hundred and twelve traders were interviewed at Maame Krobo and thirty seven of the respondents were males.

Traders' classification according to seasons

Bushmeat trade is largely affected by the hunting seasons. The trade is greatly affected by the availability of bushmeat in the market. Many traders join the market during the opened season. This period which starts at the beginning of December also coincides with the off farming season. This makes many people to engage in hunting and it results in an increase in the quantity of bushmeat in the markets. Again the dry season is at its severest period during this time and hunting with bushfires becomes the major means of killing animals. This also contributes to the quantity of bushmeat in the markets since this method kills animals indiscriminately and hunters do not need major and expensive inputs such as purchase of guns and ammunitions in

carrying out their trade. Table 5 shows the distribution of bushmeat traders according to the two hunting seasons.

Table 5: Trader classification according to hunting seasons

Hunting season	Frequency	Percent
Opened season	180	79.3
Closed season	47	20.7
Total	227	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

A total of 180 traders (79.3%) were interviewed in the opened season. Of this number 72 were males while 108 were females. For the closed season traders, 18 were males and 29 were females. Maame Krobo which had the highest respondents of 112 also had a high opened season traders of 87. It was observed that most of the opened season traders were also part-time traders while most closed season traders were fulltime traders. The Amantin market had the highest percentage (27.8%) of closed season traders as compared to the lowest 15.4% from the Tato market. The other three markets of Atebubu, Maame Krobo and Kajaji had their closed season traders' percentage to be 16.4%, 22.3% and 20.1% respectively.

Species traded at the markets

A total of 4,758 individuals comprising of 17 different species were identified as items of bushmeat trade in the five markets for the eight month study period. The recordings were made from actual observations for the six different times that the study teams visited each market and traders own

recordings. After the first visit to each of the market, traders were asked to record all other purchases made which were for the period between the previous visits and the next visit. Table 6 shows the species traded in the five markets.

Table 6: Species and their biological families

Family	Species	Frequency	Percent
Rodentia	Grasscutter	3271	68.7
	Giant Rat	459	9.6
	G. Squirrel	45	0.9
	B.T Porcupine	50	1.1
Artiodactyla	R.F Duiker	383	8.0
	Bushbuck	148	3.1
	Warthog	54	1.2
	R.R Hog	73	1.5
	Kob	14	0.4
	Waterbuck	8	0.2
	M. Duiker	5	0.1
Primata	P. Monkey	40	0.8
	G. Monkey	35	0.7
	Baboon	14	0.4
Phasianidae	Guinea Fowl	98	2.1
Lagomorpha	Togo Hare	16	0.3
Pteropodidae	Bat	45	0.9
Total		4758	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

The 17 species traded at the five markets were made up of six families. There were four species of rodents, seven species of artiodactyls, three species of primates and a lagomorph. The rest were a species of phasianide and pteropodide. Table 6 shows the distribution of the species traded and their biological families. The study recorded only one bird species-the guinea fowl and all other recordings were mammal species. No recordings were made for reptiles and amphibians.

The markets are dominated by rodents which constitute 80.3% (from table 6) of all species traded even though they make up only four of the seventeen species recorded. Grasscutter alone contributed 68.7% of the total trade from the rodents. This confirms studies done by Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998) and Swenson (2005) where they reported that rodents dominate the bushmeat trade in Ghana. The findings also show a clear sign of dwindling numbers of all wildlife species. Rodents are resilient and their recruitment rates are quite high and are therefore able to withstand the pressures of habitat destruction and hunting. The highest number of grasscutters was recorded at the Maame Krobo market with total individuals of 1,013 while the lowest figure of 400 was recorded at the Tato market.

The artiodactyls were the second largest group of mammals recorded in the markets. They constituted 14.5% of the total trade. The red flanked duiker had recordings of 383 (8%) individuals followed by the bushbuck with 148 (3.1%) individuals. Species such as the Maxwell duiker which in the past were common had the lowest recording of 5 individuals. The Maxwell duiker is a typical forest species which cannot thrive under disturbed areas and this confirms Asibey and Child (1990) assertion that indiscriminate felling of trees

decrease wildlife numbers as habitat decreases and inaccessible places open up leading to increases in hunting. The study area has experienced habitat destruction especially through bushfires over the years. However, the bushbuck and the red flanked duiker can withstand habitat changes and actually increase in numbers in areas such as farmlands. Prins and Reitsma (1989) in Asibey and Child (1990) have stated that some forest management practices and techniques tend to increase wildlife numbers while others cause wildlife population to decline. For example, selective timber extraction, which enhances vegetation growth, favours increases in the populations of many forest animals. The highest number of Red flanked duikers (209) individuals was traded at the Kajaji market. The same market recorded the highest number of Bushbucks sales of 71 individuals and total of 21 individuals of Warthog. The Tato market recorded the second highest figures for the three species. The trade in bushmeat is based on availability of species, as traders will buy any species they come across. Even though consumers may have special preferences for certain species, most people eat the bushmeat as a necessity (Ntiamoah-Baidu 1998) and the high demand give traders the leverage to trade in all species. The high numbers of the three species of the red flanked duiker, Warthog and the bushbuck call for concerns in the rate at which they are being hunted. The Kajaji and the Tato markets are closer to the Digya National Park and the park could be a source of recruitment of the species to adjoining farmlands or that hunters might be taking their hunting expeditions into the park.

Three species of primates were recorded as items of bushmeat. Together they form a small proportion of 1.9% of all species recorded. Patas

Monkey had recordings of 40 individuals and this particular species was traded in all the five markets. Green monkey and Baboon were recorded in two markets-Kajaji and the Tato. The same reasons for the high numbers of Bushbuck, Red flanked duiker and Warthog recordings in the two markets could be attributed to the recordings of the two primates in the same markets. A total of 45 individuals of bat (Pteropodidae) were recorded in only one market-Maame Krobo. The bat is a delicacy in the area hence the recordings.

Conservation status of species traded at the markets

The study failed to record any wholly protected species according to the hunting regulations of Ghana. The Grasscutter and the bat are not placed under any schedule of the hunting regulation. The Grasscutter is considered as pest to most farm crops. It is the only species where hunting is allowed throughout the whole year however; it is only licensed hunters who are allowed to hunt the species.

Species under schedule one on the hunting regulation are wholly protected and their hunting is absolutely prohibited throughout all times. The survey failed to record any of such species being traded at the market. Is this a confirmation of Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998) assertion that population of the key species exploited as bushmeat has declined over the years? Or could it be that operators hid their wares which might have contained these species or it is simply a real compliance of the law? If the latter possibility of regulation compliance is the real case, then it is really good for the wildlife conservation effort in Ghana. But if it is that traders hid their activities, then the first scheduled species of which most are vulnerable, endangered, or are

threatened, then there is the need to prevent the extinction of these species.

Table 7 shows the species traded in the markets and their conservation status.

Table 7: Conservation status of species traded at the markets

Species	Conservation status of species		
	First schedule	Second schedule	Third schedule
Grasscutter			
R.F Duiker		×	
Bushbuck		×	
Warthog		×	
R.R. Hog		×	
B.T Porcupine		×	
P. Monkey		×	
Giant Rat			×
Ground Squirrel			×
Kob		×	
Waterbuck		×	
Baboon			×
Maxwell Duiker		×	
Togo Hare		×	
Guinea Fowl			×
Bat			
Green Monkey		×	

Source: Wildlife conservation regulation, 1971; LI 685 and field data 2007

Schedule two species are species of which capturing or destroying of any of them is absolutely prohibited between 1st August and 1st December (closed season) in any year. It is also illegal to hunt any young animal or an adult accompanied by its young under the schedule. Eleven of the species traded at the markets fall under this category.

Third scheduled species are those which are absolutely protected during the closed season. Four species traded at the market were recorded under this schedule. They are two rodents, a bird and a primate. The Baboon is the only primate which is classified under this category and this is due to its biological characteristics such as a high fecundity rate and again it is considered as a pest to farm crops as the rodents. Notwithstanding the conservation status of the species, a hunting license is required before one can hunt any of the species except for those under schedule one.

Species traded according to hunting seasons

Of the total of 4758 individuals traded at the five markets, 30.6% were traded in the closed season. With the exception of the Grasscutter which could be hunted all season provided the hunter had a requisite permit/license, all the other species traded at the markets were illegal. Apart from the Baboon which was not recorded in the closed season, all species recorded in the opened season were also recorded in the closed season (see Table 8).

Table 8: Species traded at the hunting seasons

Species	Opened season		Closed season	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Grasscutter	2416	70.9	855	63.3
Giant Rat	313	9.2	146	10.8
G. Squirrel	24	0.7	21	1.5
B.T Porcupine	41	1.2	9	0.7
R.F Duiker	250	7.3	133	9.8
Bushbuck	100	2.9	48	3.6
Warthog	37	1.1	17	1.3
R.R Hog	50	1.5	23	1.7
Kob	8	0.2	6	0.4
Waterbuck	7	0.2	1	0.1
M. Duiker	3	0.1	2	0.1
P. Monkey	26	0.8	14	1.0
G. Monkey	15	0.4	20	1.6
Baboon	14	0.4	0	0.0
Guinea Fowl	74	2.2	24	1.8
Togo Hare	7	0.2	9	0.7
Bat	23	0.7	22	1.6
Total	3408	100	1350	100

Source: Field survey, 2007

The grasscutter dominated in the two seasons but the overall percentage of the species reduced in the closed season from 70.9% in the opened season to 63.3%. In absolute figures, the total number of individuals of grasscutter traded in the closed season is nearly a third of individuals traded in

the opened season. The high species numbers in the opened season is due to the rate at which hunting is conducted in the communities of study area during the opened season. In the opened season which also coincides with the off farming season, most people especially the youth embark on group hunting and this leads to a high increase of grasscutter supply to the markets. Also fire is a major hunting tool during this period which means hunters do not need high inputs of hunting gears before embarking on their trade. Over all there is an increase in hunting effort during this period either by increase in numbers of hunters or hunters move to longer distances before getting their kill (Ntiamoh-Baidu, 1998).

Hunters are not selective in their operation and will kill any animal irrespective of the conservation status of the species (Ntiamoah-Baidu, 1998). With the exception of Brush tailed porcupine, the Guinea fowl, the Baboon and the Waterbuck which percentages decreased during the closed season, all other species had their percentages increasing. This is a very worrying situation since in the first place all the hunted species apart from the grasscutter was illegal and also their percentage contribution increased in a prohibited period. Primates are one of the most threatened mammal families but from Table 8 two primate species were traded in the market during the closed season. In one instance the numbers of green monkeys traded in the closed season (1.6%) were more than what was traded in the opened season (0.4%).

The highest closed season trading of prohibited species in the period was recorded at the Kajaji market with 179 individuals forming 36.2% of prohibited species. The lowest recording was at Atebubu market with 11.5%

of all prohibited species traded at the five markets. The single most prohibited traded species in the closed season at the Kajaji market is the red flanked duiker with 64 individuals.

Freshly killed species and their reproductive status

Data was taken on freshly killed species to determine their reproductive status. Species were first examined for their sexual status, that is, whether female or male. Not many species were observed as freshly killed animals. Most of the bigger animals were processed at the point of kill before sending to the market. However, freshly killed rodents were observed in the markets. Table 9 shows species observed and their reproductive status. The aim of the exercise was to examine how effective the closed season period coincides with the reproductive period of the species. However, the study was deficient in data because there was not a continuous data collection to be able to make concrete findings.

Table 9: Species observed as freshly killed

Species	Frequency	Percent
Grasscutter	59	39.2
Giant rat	66	44.0
B.T Porcupine	1	0.7
Ground Squirrel	3	2.0
R.F. Duiker	6	4.0
Togo Hare	1	0.7
Bats	7	4.7
Guinea Fowl	7	4.7
Total	150	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

Three males and three females of the red flanked duiker species were recorded. Two of the females were recorded in the closed season and none was either pregnant or lactating. The recordings for the guinea fowl had two females and seven males. However the issue of pregnancy and lactation could not be applicable to a bird.

A total of 150 individuals made up of eight species were observed before they were processed for the market. Out of the total individuals observed, 47 were males. Out of the 103 females observed as freshly killed animals only 9 were pregnant and 12 were lactating. For the lactating mothers, nine were grasscutters while three were giant rats. Also for the pregnant individuals, they were three grasscutters and six giant rats. The pregnant grasscutters were all recorded in the opened season compared to four lactating mothers. For the six pregnant giant rats, four were observed in the closed season and two in the opened season. These findings do not give a clear picture of the effectiveness of the closed season to the reproductive status of the species. Rodents normally get pregnant for at least three consecutive times in a year. One female of ground squirrel was recorded in the opened season and it was not pregnant, the rest of the species recordings were males.

Traders' knowledge on hunting methods

Hunting methods are regulated in Ghana. The hunting method regulations target both the hunting gear used such as prohibiting the use of gin traps, wire snares and even regulating the use of the approved method of gunshot. For example, it is illegal to use light in hunting. This implicitly makes hunting in the night with a hunting lamp illegal, even with the approved

method of gunshot. Table 10 shows respondents' level of knowledge on hunting methods regulation. The question was asked for traders to name the hunting methods they know and for which they have encountered meat killed by that method before. This question had multiple responses and the total recording was 693 out of possible 1108 responses from the four methods provided.

Table 10: Traders' awareness on hunting methods

Hunting methods	Frequency	Percent
Gunshot	227	32.8
Trap/snare	206	29.7
Poisoned	152	21.9
Group hunting	108	15.6
Total	693	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

All respondents (227) mentioned gunshot as the most known method and this formed 32.8% of the total counts of responses. Traps and the use of snares were the next hunting method with 29.7%. Surprisingly, the most dangerous of all hunting methods was the use of poison to kill animals which received the third spot. The poisoned method received 152 confirmations from the respondents. Traders mentioned that in the past hunters were using local concoction to kill animals especially grasscutter, however, most now use chemicals. The detail of the local concoction preparation is presented in the section on hunters' hunting methods.

When traders were asked whether they buy all meat irrespective of the hunting method, 79.3% of respondents answered in the positive while 20.7% said no. The reasons given by those who buy all meat irrespective of the hunting method were varied. Some claimed that they are not experienced enough to determine poisoned meat, besides there are no clear cut methods to test meat which has been poisoned at the market place. Some also contended that poisoned meat is not harmful to human since the chemicals used are not dangerous to human health. Also in processing the meat they throw all the stomach content away and therefore the chemical does not get into the real meat itself. This clearly supports Mensah's (2003) report in the Daily Guide Newspaper that most animals in Ghana are hunted with dangerous chemicals.

Those who said they would reject any meat killed by poison mentioned that they are experienced enough to detect poisoned meat by just looking at the colour of the smoked meat which looks more darkened than usual and the colour is not as a result of soot from smoke. Besides, unprocessed meat which is killed by poison shows no traces of either gunshot or other marks which suggest that they were killed by snare/traps or clubbed. They also contended that it is unethical to sell meat which is poisoned to consumers.

For the other methods such as the use of traps and snares as well as group hunting methods, traders did not see anything wrong, and none of them said they would reject meat killed by any of these methods. Table 11 shows responses on how hunting methods affect meat quality.

Table 11: Effects of hunting methods on meat quality

Hunting methods	Frequency	Percent
Gunshot	159	70.0
Trap/snare	28	12.3
Group hunting	22	9.7
Undecided	18	7.9
Total	227	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

Traders were asked to mention the method which makes the best meat. Gunshot had the highest rating with 70.0%. Respondents' reason for choosing this method of hunting is that normally gunshot meat is processed on time and even during processing ammunitions is removed. Trap/ snare received the second highest response and traders' reason was that sometimes trapped meat gets rotten before hunters retrieved the animals for processing. Group hunting which uses a combination of methods received third rating. 7.9% of respondents were undecided on the hunting methods with regards to meat quality. It is ironic that no one mentioned poisoned meat as a method which makes quality meat even though some traders had defended this method and had argued that the method has no adverse effects on consumers. Such traders may fall within the undecided group.

Traders' knowledge on hunting regulations

The study sought to assess the traders' knowledge of hunting regulations of Ghana. The hunting regulations of Ghana thrive on five main themes. They are closed season, prohibited hunting methods, prohibited

hunted species, and prohibited hunting area and license requirements. Traders were asked to mention any of the regulations they know and what each regulation entails. This had multiple responses as can be read from Table 12.

Table 12: Traders' knowledge of hunting regulations

Hunting regulations	Frequency	Percent
Closed season	197	22.8
Hunting in prohibited area	170	19.7
Prohibited hunting method	110	12.7
Prohibited hunting species	164	19.0
License requirement	224	25.8
Total	865	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

For the five hunting regulation themes the total possible responses would have been 1135, had all the 227 traders been able to mention every regulation. However, the total responses were 865 which represent 76.2%. This confirms Ntiamoah-Baidu findings in 1998 that operators of the bushmeat trade have a high level of awareness of hunting regulations in areas where the Wildlife Division is present. It was found out that those who had little experience of the bushmeat trade (those who have been operating in less than three years) had little knowledge of the hunting regulations. None of the hunting regulations received a 100% mention from the respondents.

The need to have a license before one can trade received the highest mention (224/227). This is not surprising as this is the regulation which most affects the bushmeat trade. Occasionally traders are checked by the officials of

the Wildlife Division to ensure that they have the requisite license. Some traders who have not acquired license have had their goods seized by the Wildlife Division and sold to the general public. Traders are therefore particular about this regulation. The Atebubu market had a 100% mention of the license requirement and the closed season regulations. This could be explained by the presence of the Digya National Park headquarters in the town and the long association the town has had with Wildlife Division.

When traders were asked where they acquire their licenses, they mentioned the Wildlife Division. This is in contravention of Act 462 which gives the District Assemblies the right to issue bushmeat license to the traders. The Wildlife Division devolved this right to the District Assemblies in 1990 in an attempt to decentralize that responsibility and also to retain some revenue from bushmeat to the districts and the local communities. The District Assemblies have shirked this responsibility. Under this arrangement the District Assemblies were to retain 80% of the revenue generated while they pay 20% to government chest. Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998) in a study in 40 districts to find out the district which had issued bushmeat license to traders could not indicate a particular project that the revenue had been spent on. Also the study found out that about 50% of the district surveyed did not know that they had that responsibility and those who knew it simply failed to carry out this directive. The district finance offices where this study was carried out (Atebubu-Amantin, Sene and Kwahu North District assemblies) were contacted on the issuance of bushmeat license and the response was that they know that this directive exists but because the Wildlife Division has offices in

all the three districts, they have not carried out this directive thinking that the Wildlife Division will collect the license fees.

Traders at Atebubu, Kwame Danso and Dorkorkrom had no problem in acquiring license as the Wildlife Division has offices in these towns. When traders were asked about the difficulty they go through in acquiring license, respondents said the fees charged for the species were moderate and have no difficulty in acquiring license. However, traders who do not come from these towns mentioned the difficulty of traveling to these towns before acquiring licenses. They said for some of them the lorry fare is even higher than the license fees they are to pay. They also reported harassment from wildlife officials at certain times. Traders from Accra who mostly patronized the Maame Krobo market get their licenses from the headquarters of the Wildlife Division.

The closed season regulation received the second highest awareness mentioned. A total of 197/227 (86.8%) traders said they know about this regulation. Traders were asked to mention the period for which this regulation is applied. Most were able to mention the beginning (1st August) of the period but failed in the ending of the period (1st December). Most of the time traders thought the end of the period is 31st December. Swenson (2005) in similar study at the Techiman market found out that 20.6% respondents could not mention the period of closed season correctly, but all the respondents (34) knew that there is period where hunting is not permitted on certain species except the grasscutter. This information affects revenue generation as most traders come for license for species other than the grasscutter, in January to

July while ground evidence shows that intensive hunting and trading normally starts before December.

Regulations on hunting methods, prohibited hunting area and prohibited hunting species received high awareness returns (48 %). This is readily attributed to the law enforcement measures that the Wildlife Division sometimes carried out. On a regulation of prohibited hunted species, respondents mostly mentioned the primates and tree pangolin (*Manis tricuspis*) as the prohibited hunted species. However, of the thirteen primates' species known to exist in Ghana, six of them do not fall under the first schedule of the hunting regulations. Prohibited hunted area received the third highest mention, and this could be attributed to the law enforcement measures of the Wildlife Division since some traders and hunters have had some encounters with the law.

Bushmeat licensing and trade illegalities

Bushmeat traders are required to get a bushmeat trading license before they can operate. The study sought to look at the effectiveness of the licensing system. Generally the licensing system does not require operators to submit returns on their operations to the licensing authority (Wildlife Division and the District Assemblies) and therefore traders flout the regulations under which the license is issued. License issued expires within six months starting from the date of issued. But traders are expected to renew their licenses immediately they have bought all species upon which the license was issued even when the stipulated period has not expired. The license also specifies among other things species to be purchased and that purchases should also be

from only licensed hunters. Under the current circumstance traders will only renew their license after the expired period or a Wildlife Division staff accidentally or purposively meets a trader and takes stock of purchases. Any excess purchase is confiscated and the license is cancelled. Table 13 shows the results of the survey on traders on the licensing system.

Table 13: Illegalities of the bushmeat trade license

Illegalities	Frequency	Percent
Expired license	73	32.2
Traders without license	22	9.7
Species outside license	132	58.1
Total	227	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

Out of the 227 traders interviewed, 32.2% had licenses which had expired with an expiry date range of between two months and two years. An expired license is a license which has been transferred from one season to another. This unlawful trading practice was recorded in all the five markets with highest recording at the Maame Krobo market. Out of the 112 traders interviewed at the Maame Krobo market 32.1% had their licenses expired. Bushmeat traders acquire most of their trading license during the opened season especially between January and March. Since the closed season regulation does not allow trading in other species apart from the grasscutter, traders carried their licenses which would have been expired at the end of July to the closed season. The difficulty with this is that licenses are supposed to last for a period of six months, but certain species are not allowed to be

purchased during certain period and traders who acquire their licenses for species other than the grasscutter after January would not be able to use the license for the six month period. This may be a loss to some traders who were not able to purchase all the species upon which the license was issued. However, traders who were candid mentioned that they are able to use their licenses for about four trips to market centres within a month, and a lucky trader could purchase all that one had been issued a license for. This implicitly shows that the traders are able to exhaust all purchases before their licenses expired. Therefore, the non-renewal based on the inability to purchase all species issued with license is untenable.

However, there were licensed traders who bought species outside what their licenses stipulated. They even formed the largest group (58.1%) of unlawful trading practices with regards to the licensing system. Traders who acquired license mostly come for grasscutter license and few add the red flanked duiker, the bushbuck, and the other rodents. The fee charged for the grasscutter and the other rodents is ₪1000.00 and this is relatively cheap which makes most traders go for these species permits. Also this species are fairly abundant and traders will easily get such species to purchase. However traders will buy all species they come across irrespective of what species their licenses stipulate. Out of the 227 traders interviewed, 20.3% had had their meat confiscated before by the Wildlife Division for either purchasing more than what their license stipulates or operating without licenses.

Hunters and hunting activities

A total of 49 hunters were interviewed from the five markets from which this study was undertaken. All hunters interviewed were males. The mean age of the hunters was 39 years (range 17 to 65 years). Length of hunting experience ranged from between one year and fifty years with the mean hunting years being 11 years. Most hunters (71.4%) are part time hunters with other occupations such as farmers, artisans and fishermen. Only 28.6% of the interviewed hunters were full time hunters. The bulk of the part time hunters were farmers (29). The distribution of hunters according to their locations is seen Table 14.

Table 14: Distribution of hunters by location

Location	Hunters (No.)	Percent
Atebubu	18	36.7
Maame Krobo	12	24.5
Kajaji	7	14.3
Tato	4	8.2
Amantin	8	16.3
Total	49	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

Atebubu had the highest recordings of hunters with 36.7% whilst the least (8.2%) was at Tato. Hunters were normally not found at the markets and they were located in the towns where the study was conducted. Sometimes popular hunters were located in hamlets which were not close to the towns where the study was conducted. There are four basic hunting methods

identified in the study area, namely group hunting, the use of guns, snare/traps and poisonous chemicals.

The group hunting method involved a group of people who use a combination of hunting gears such as spears, cutlasses, guns, clubs and dogs. This is a highly dangerous method not only to the animals but also to the human operators. This method is highly indiscriminate as hunters swoop on every animal they have surrounded after making a hunting belt around an area they suspect to habit animals. They will then use the dogs to track the animals or they will set fire to flush out the animal. There are a lot of human casualties as hunters get shot by colleagues accidentally. The study failed to locate and interview any of these groups in the study area. These groups usually move to long distances sometimes in vehicles to carry out their trade. This made locating them difficult since they are not stationary.

The most common hunting method used by the 49 hunters interviewed was gunshot. All the respondents use gun which is the approved method in their operations. Even though all the hunters use gun to hunt, not all of them own gun. Most of the hunters who do not own guns are part time hunters who depend on hired or borrowed guns to undertake their work. Such hunters either pay cash for the use of the gun or may have to share the catch with the gun owner. Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998) made similar findings where all professional hunters owned gun while young/ part time hunters borrowed guns from the older hunters and paid portions of their catch to the gun owners.

The use of wire snares or traps is another common hunting method in the study area. About 59% of the part time hunters who were also farmers used snares or traps. The use of snares and traps are not limited to

farmer/hunters alone, but some full time hunters also use them. Farmer/hunters set a barrier around their farms after which they intersperse the barrier with either the snare or the trap. This method which is mainly used to protect the farms of hunters is also illegal since this method is indiscriminate and sometimes dangerous to humans. Traps are visited daily or as often as hunter is able to. Full time hunters who also set traps usually set their traps in bushes and in the forest. There are two types of these, sometimes traps/snare are purposefully set on animal track/trail or when hunter wants to set many traps/snares he would cut a track himself in the bushes or forest and set a number of traps/snares on the track. The distances between such traps/snares are between five and ten meters interval.

Poisonous chemicals are also used in killing animals. At first hunters used local concoction made up of the roots of some plants especially the milk bush plant (*Thevitia spp.*) and a mixture of urine and salt. Urine which has lasted for about three days or more is mixed with a mash of the bark of the plant roots and together with salt and spread on a ground where a hunter suspect especially grasscutters inhabit the area. The salt lick formed attracts the animals and as they lick the ground the poison kills them. However, nowadays with the advent of pesticides on the market, hunters use them together with salt to form salt lick to kill animals. Two freshly grasscutters observed at the Maame Krobo market were suspected to have been killed by poison since the animals did not bear any marks which would have suggested that they might have been killed by the other methods.

The success rates of the different hunting methods vary and the species composition of hunters' catch may also depend upon the hunting methods. Of

the 150 freshly killed individuals, 86 were shot, 62 were snared or trapped and 2 were poisoned. In the study area the most common hunting method is the use of gun but usually smaller game are hunted by the use of dogs and fire. Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998), made similar findings where out of 1,192 carcasses observed, 50% were shot, 12% were trapped and the rest were caught by dogs or killed with cutlasses. In this study all the giant rats were either trapped or where killed by dogs whilst the red flanked duikers were all shot.

When hunters' were asked about their knowledge of the hunting methods they are using as per the hunting methods regulation, all hunters were unanimous that the gunshot method is the best among all the methods. However, 86.7% were not aware that hunting by either in group or the use of snares and traps were also against the law. The contention was that farmers need to protect their crops from pest and therefore snaring and trapping is one of the surest ways they can do that. Also the argument was that the purchase of gun and its ammunition is quite an expensive venture which is beyond the reach power of most rural dwellers. Currently, the cost of a locally manufactured gun is between two million and three million cedis. They contended that currently a hunter with a gun would incur a cost of between one hundred and two hundred cedis to undertake a three day hunting expedition. Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998) reports that the hunter incurs both capital and recurrent cost in the hunting business and the main capital cost is the acquisition of a gun. She continues that the recurrent cost of the hunter was mainly hunting accessories such as torchlight, batteries, ammunition, carbide, matches and in some cases transportation to hunting site and to markets. Of these items three of them: ammunition, batteries and carbide constitute about

80% of the total recurrent cost of the hunter. The average hunting cost per week in towns was about ₵9,000 and in a city it was ₵11,400 (Ntiamoah-Baidu 1998). With these figures as a guideline and taken into account the inflationary pressures over the years then it could be said that the hunters were giving accurate figures in their hunting cost.

Hunting activity is undertaken day and night in the forest and the bushes. Hunting is also done in the farmlands. Hunting in the night is illegal in Ghana. The hunting regulation states that it is against the law for any person to hunt using any artificial light or flare. However, none of the forty nine hunters was aware that there was a law against the use of light for hunting let alone hunting in the night. Hunters who hunt in the night usually leave home at dusk, hunt all night and return the next morning. When asked why they hunt at the night, 78.9% of the hunters said success rate is high for night hunting and this finding is corroborated by Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998).

Hunters' catch and disposal methods

A total of 2571 animals comprising sixteen species were recorded from the 49 hunters interviewed during the eight month study period in five markets that were studied. The total records for hunters' catch falls short by 2187 individuals of all species traded in the five markets. Actually the total kill from hunters interviewed was 54.0% of the bushmeat supply recorded at the market for the study period (see Table 15).

Table 15: Species harvested by hunters

Species	Frequency	Percent
Grasscutter	1617	62.9
Giant Rat	306	9.8
G. Squirrel	53	2.1
B.T Porcupine	37	1.4
R.F Duiker	165	8.5
Bushbuck	70	2.7
Warthog	38	1.5
R.R Hog	38	1.5
Kob	9	0.3
Waterbuck	9	0.3
M. Duiker	3	0.1
P. Monkey	19	0.8
G. Monkey	25	1.0
Baboon	10	0.4
Guinea Fowl	133	5.2
Togo Hare	39	1.5
Total	2571	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

Bushmeat harvesting and supply is not solely the work of those who are professional hunters but any one who gets the chance of killing an animal at a particular time may sell meat to the market. During the opened season when there is little farm work many people engage in hunting activities. The excess 2187 animal individuals which were supplied to the market but which

were not recorded from the interviewed hunters might have been supplied by other professional hunters who were difficult to locate and hence not interviewed. But the bulk of the supply would have come from group hunters. Group hunters sometimes sojourn for many days and even those who return the same day normally come late and all these might have led to the inability of the study team to interview them. Table 15 above shows the number of species and individuals harvested by the hunters. No bat was recorded from the hunters catch however, 45 individuals of the species were recorded at the market.

Animals killed by a hunter may be either sold in whole or in parts depending on the size of the animals. The hunter and his family could also eat animals killed. Usually the medium size and the large game are sold while the smaller game such as the rodents is eaten by the hunter (Asibey and child, 1990; Ntiamoah-Baidu, 1998). Of the hunters' catch, 19.5% of the animals were eaten by the hunter and his family while the rest was either sold or small proportion (7.2%) was given as a gift mostly to gun owners.

Hunters' awareness of hunting regulations

Restrictions and regulations on hunting in Ghana is regulated by the wildlife conservation regulations of 1971 with the legislative instrument Act 685. Hunters were asked of their awareness of any of the regulations. Table 16 shows hunters' responses to the hunting regulations. The percentage calculations are over the total responses generated for the responses and not the total number of hunters (49). However, frequencies for each response are counted out of the total number of hunters interviewed.

Table 16: Hunters' awareness on hunting regulations

Hunting regulations	Frequency	Percent
Closed season	46	25.0
Hunting in prohibited area	49	26.6
Prohibited hunting method	12	6.5
Prohibited hunting species	28	15.3
License requirement	49	26.6
Total	184	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2007

The highest response for a regulation were two regulations-license requirement and hunting in a prohibited area. Even though license/permit requirement regulation had 49/49 responses none of the hunters had a valid license for their operations. Thirteen (26.5%) out of the total had acquired license before but the expiry dates of these licenses ranged between a low of two years to a high of eleven years. When asked why hunters are not acquiring licenses before they embark on their trade, the reasons were varied ranging from inefficiency of the Wildlife Division to enforce the regulations to administrative procedures that hunters must go through in acquiring gun license at the Ghana Police Service.

Hunters mentioned that when Act 462 was enacted empowering the District Assemblies to generate revenue from the use of natural resources in their districts, the target of the Assemblies was on the bushmeat traders and not the hunters and the Wildlife Division which should have issued the license/permit to hunters shirked this responsibility. This led hunters who should have still gone for license before hunting to escape without paying for

the permit. Also hunters normally sell their catch in their homes and sometimes in their hunting camps (Ntiamoah-Baidu, 1998). This makes it difficult for the Wildlife Division to arrest hunters who flout the law; actually there is more likelihood for a trader without license to be arrested than a hunter. Traders' trade either in the market or at specific spot or may transport their wares to certain places/markets and therefore these expose them to the likelihood of being arrested if they do not have the requisite permit. One other thing which has not been taken into account is, in situations where the hunter and the trader are both charged for a permit which could amount to a charge on the same species; could it be a double taxation? A hunter is required to acquire permit for species to be killed and at the same time a trader is issued a permit to purchase bushmeat from only a licensed hunter, therefore a species is charged twice in this circumstance.

Again for a hunter to be issued a permit to hunt, he needs to provide evidence that he is the lawful owner of a gun. A section of the Act 685 (section 7, sub section 1) reads that 'the chief game officer shall not grant a license to an applicant to hunt with firearms unless the applicant satisfies him that he is lawfully in possession of a license granted under the regulation 59 or 60 of the Arms and Ammunition Regulations, 1962 (L.I 200), authorizing him to use a firearm for the period for which he requires hunting license.' The Ghana Police Service is the authority to provide the applicant a license to use gun.

With the above premise hunters find it difficult to acquire licenses to hunt because according to Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998) guns that hunters are using as at that time were acquired between 1970 and 1997. This means most of the

guns in use today were not acquired by the users of today as most of the real owners might have passed on with time. Also there is the problem of hunters borrowing guns to hunt; they may find it difficult to gain gun licenses for guns which they do not personally own from the Police. Guns which may be fairly new would not have been purchased at an authorized shop, but may be the work of a local blacksmith which has been illegalized. This makes it all the more difficult for hunters to acquire gun licenses which is a prerequisite for acquiring a hunting license. This situation is similar to the findings of Akumsi (2003), which state that a gun license is required as a prerequisite to acquiring hunting permits in the Cameroon; however local manufactured guns are widely used by hunters and these guns are not recognized by the administration and therefore cannot be issued gun licenses. The local hunters are therefore left with the only option of illegal hunting, using local guns that they can easily purchase. These findings are also in line with those by Asibey and Child (1990) which criticise the effect of such legislation which criminalizes the traditional utilization of wildlife by either ignoring or defining wildlife utilization as poaching and the technologies used in hunting declared as unlawful methods of hunting.

Hunting in a prohibited area also received highest mention of 49/49. This could be explained with the presence of the Digya National Park in the study area which is a symbol of the Wildlife Division presence in the study area. In fact 7 of the hunters interviewed had ever been arrested before by the Wildlife Division staff for wrongful entry into the Digya National Park. One of those arrested was sentenced to a six months imprisonment while the rest were fined between ₪400,000.00 and ₪600,000.00 by a magistrate court.

Poaching activities at the Digya National Park

The study also covered the activities of poachers in the Digya National Park. Figure 3 shows the arrest of illegal hunters and other illegal activities at the Digya National Park for a ten year period. In 1961 the Wild Animals Preservation Act, 1961 (Act 43) was formulated to more firmly secure wildlife by conserving representative samples of the varied ecosystems of Ghana in protected areas. Also the Wildlife Reserves Regulations L.I.710 of 1971 and Wildlife Conservation Regulations L.I 685 also of 1971 were gazetted. It is these regulations that the Digya National Park and other protected areas manage wildlife species within and outside the park. These laws prevent all persons from entering a protected area unless they have been given permit by an appropriate authority (Wildlife Division).

Figure: 3 Illegal activities in the Digya National Park between 1998 and 2007

Source: Digya office 2007

For the study period, a total of 209 poachers were arrested by the park management. Poachers' offences usually include illegal entry (100% for all poachers), setting of fires to bushes (4.5%), and killing of animals (67.2%). Also poachers are charged with illegal entry with dangerous weapons (guns, cutlasses, spears, knives and traps/snares) which could harm animals- 82.4%. From the graph the highest peak of poaching activity was in 2000 with 32 poachers being arrested. Also the lowest number of poachers was in 2004 with 6 poachers being arrested for the year.

The number of poachers was at the highest peak at 2000 because during that period there was a change in the management of the park and as is always the case with most organizations when management changes there is an increase in patrol activities leading to a number of arrests also increasing. Generally the number of poachers decreased from the 2000 peak to 2004 low until it started rising again to a high of 30 in 2007. Poachers usually assess their chances of escaping arrest in their operations before they will embark on their activities (Jachmann, 2007). Therefore with the increase in the number of anti-poaching activities, poaching will definitely reduce for the period. However, it could also be said that poaching activities actually did not reduce over the 2000 to 2004 but rather poachers were able to evade arrest due to laxity on the part of the field staff after the initial success. Poachers when arrested are prosecuted at the law courts. Court convictions ranged from fines to imprisonment terms. The lowest of the court fines was ₺30,000.00 in 1998 for illegal entry to the highest fine of ₺2,400,000.00 in 2005. Usually fines are the main penalties that the courts give to poachers. However, under rare circumstances when poachers have killed threatened species or have set fire in

the vegetation of the park the court convicts them into prison terms. Depending on the severity of the poachers' action, the term of imprisonment range from three months to three years.

For the period under consideration 48 poachers were observed in the park but the field staff failed to arrest them. Sometimes poachers run away and leave behind their guns and other weapons. From the graph the highest number of poachers that escaped was in 2000 with eleven poachers escaping. Incidentally it was the same year that the highest number of poachers was arrested.

Hunting and bushmeat trade license revenue from Digya

The Wildlife Division keeps records of hunting and bushmeat trade licenses. The study took data on revenue generated from bushmeat trade and hunting license from 1998 to 2007. Such records provide data on the number of licenses and number of each species covered by the license. The total number of licenses issued varied from year to year. The licensing system does not require hunters to provide returns on the animals they kill or traded in. There is also no way of monitoring compliance by the operators on the numbers and species permitted to kill. In 1990, the Wildlife Division devolved the issuance of bushmeat trade licenses to the district assemblies in attempt to decentralize that responsibility and also to return some revenue for the local authority by taking 80% while paying 20% to the government. Operators of the bushmeat trade are to pay a minimum of ₪1000.00 for grasscutter to a high of ₪350,000.00 for buffalo. Figure 4 shows the revenue generated by the Digya National Park for the ten year period.

Figure 4: Revenue generation from bushmeat/ hunting license at Digya

Source: Digya office 2007

Over the period, revenue generation increased in absolute terms from a low of ₵453,800.00 to a high of ₵36,398,000.00. For the study period, fees charged had not been reviewed. The early years between 1998 and 2003 recorded very low revenue generation. The reason for the low revenue generation was that when the bushmeat trade license was given to the district assemblies to issue, the Wildlife Division concentrated only on the issuance of hunting license to hunters. When the District finance offices of the studied districts were contacted to get the figures for the period they were in charge of the license, the records were not available. This confirms the report of Ntiamoah-Baidu (1998) that the revenue books given to the district assemblies were not properly kept and the revenue generated is not properly accounted for. Revenue started increasing from 2004 and dipped in 2005, but has consistently risen to its highest level of ₵36,398,000.00.

The rise can be attributed to two major reasons. Firstly the Park's management has decentralized revenue generation into its three offices at Atebubu, Kwame Danso and Donkorkrom. Before 2004 revenue generation was centralized at the Park's headquarters. This was a disincentive to the operators who have to travel for a long distances to Atebubu before obtaining licenses. Sometimes the lorry fare is much more than the value of the license that the operator would buy not forgetting the risk associated with traveling. Secondly, the Wildlife Division in contravention to Act 462 is issuing licenses to the bushmeat traders taken advantage of the non performance of the district assemblies in the revenue generation even though the devolution right to the assemblies has not been revoked. Revenue generation continues to increase and especially in 2007, it reached its highest because the park management moved to the markets to issue license.

A total of 1428 licenses have been purchased over the ten year period yielding a total of ₵93,378,460.00. The maximum numbers of license are issued in the first quarter of every year. This period coincides with the opened season and bushmeat harvesting is at its peak during the period. The second quarter of the year is the lowest in terms of license purchased. License purchased lasts for six months before they expire and therefore most of the licenses purchased at the first quarter are carried over to the second quarter. The fourth quarter which begins the opened season is the second highest period for license purchased especially in December. Licensed purchased for the third quarter is for grasscutter only and even though the number of people who buy license in the period is quite appreciable the fees charged on the grasscutter-₵1000.00 is not substantial.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Study objectives and methods

This study was carried out in five markets and their environs around the Digya National Park. The study sought to evaluate wildlife hunting restrictions on bushmeat trade and hunting. The chosen markets fall in three administrative district assemblies, however they are in two political regions- the Brong Ahafo and the Eastern Regions of Ghana. The markets are the Atebubu, Amantin, Tato and Kajaji markets in the Brong Ahafo Region. The last market is the Maame Krobo in the Eastern Region.

The study sampled both traders and hunters for interview on bushmeat trade and hunting respectively. A total of 276 traders and hunters were interviewed for the period of eight months in the five markets and their environs. The two groups were made up 227 traders and 49 hunters.

Two sampling techniques were used in getting respondents for the study. These were snowballing sampling technique for sampling hunters and traders and a simple random sampling procedure for sampling dates to visit the five markets. A key informant was interviewed first and after that the team requested for the locations of people who are into the bushmeat business (hunters and traders) for them also to be interviewed.

In-depth interviews were conducted in three languages depending on the respondents' fluency of these languages-Twi, Ewe and English. The team

composition for the survey was based on the fluency of team members in these languages. Five such interviews were conducted in each market for the study period but the sixth visit was used for a focus group discussion. Team members conducted visits to chop-bars and homes of wholesalers in the towns to conduct interviews and also to have direct observations. A focus group discussion was carried out at each of the five selected markets.

Secondary data for hunting and bushmeat trading license issued by the Digya National Park were also collected and analyzed to obtain periods of increases or otherwise in hunting and trading in bushmeat. This data covered a ten-year period from 1998 to 2007.

The major findings of the study

The study failed to record any wholly protected species according to the hunting regulations of Ghana. Despite the decline in species numbers there was hunting and trading in bushmeat throughout the study period. Illegal hunting methods (snare, traps, poisoned and group hunting) are used in killing wildlife but 70.0% of respondents mentioned gunshot as the key method. All animals are hunted irrespective of their conservation status.

The grasscutter dominated the markets in the two seasons, however, the overall percentage of the species reduced in the closed season to 63.3%. In total rodents contributed 80.3% of the species traded at markets- a sign of a decline population of key species. Out of the 103 females observed as freshly killed animals only 9 were pregnant and 12 were lactating. Pregnant and lactating mothers were rodents- the grasscutter and the giant rat. There were

recordings for lactating and pregnant mothers both in the opened season and the closed season.

All species are traded in the market irrespective of the season. All species traded in the opened season were also traded in the closed season except one species. Majority of hunters (46 out of 49) and traders (197 out of 227) are aware of the closed season. But the problem is lack of compliance on the part of operators (traders and hunters) and enforcement on the part of regulatory authorities- the Wildlife Division. People who had little experience of the bushmeat trade (those who have been operating in less than three years) also had little knowledge of the hunting regulations. Most hunters are not aware of the fact that there is hunting method regulation.

Traders acquire their licenses from the Wildlife Division in contravention of Act 462 which gives the District Assemblies the right to issue bushmeat license to traders. Traders did not complain of any major hindrances in acquiring bushmeat trading licenses. Hunters however have problems of acquiring hunting licenses since it is difficult for them to acquire a weapon permit from the police which is a prerequisite for acquiring hunting license.

There are trade illegalities in the bushmeat trade. As much as 32.2% had expired licenses, 58.1% bought meat outside what their license stipulates and 9.7% had not acquired license before. All of the hunters had no valid license. The licensing system is not effective because there is no requirement of returns on licenses purchased by operators. Most of these illegalities are committed in the opened season.

Conclusions

Based on the above findings, these conclusions are drawn for the study:

- Current hunting methods are unsustainable. Hunting and trading in bushmeat is largely unregulated.
- Bushmeat market is dominated by rodents which are able to resist the couple pressures of hunting and habitat destruction.
- The closed season period is ineffective as ban species are traded openly in the markets during the period. However awareness of the existence of the period among traders and hunters is high.
- Traders' and hunters' knowledge and awareness on hunting restrictions are high and the level of awareness grows with increasing experience in the trade. Even though operators in the bushmeat trade showed awareness they still flout the restrictions with impunity.
- The Wildlife Division did not have the capacity both in material and human resources to ensure compliance of the hunting restrictions.
- Hunters had difficulty in acquiring hunting license. Regulations on procedures one has to go through in acquiring weapons permits from the Ghana Police Service do not recognize locally made guns.

Recommendations

The recommendations being proposed are based on the final conclusions drawn from the study and the immense contribution of the bushmeat industry in Ghana, especially as a major protein and income source for most rural economies. To sustain these contributions made by the

bushmeat industry there is a need for a sustainable hunting of wildlife for which these recommendations are made:

- The Wildlife Division especially the Digya National Park needs to build the capacity of its field staff to coordinate and monitor bushmeat exploitation, production and trade in markets around the Park. There is a need to create a new unit within the park's administration which will be responsible for bushmeat hunting and trade.
- The Wildlife Division management should strengthen the community collaborative resource management unit to carry out wildlife conservation education in the communities while also strengthening the law enforcement unit to ensure compliance of the hunting regulations.
- There is a need for the Wildlife Division to vigorously pursue its new Community Resource Management Areas (CREMAs) which seeks to devolve ownership and stewardship of wildlife resources to local communities with the view of ensuring community participation in wildlife management.
- The Wildlife Division should establish offices in key districts where bushmeat production is quite substantial. The Division should liaise with the District Assemblies and orientates such districts to enforce Act 462 which could generate revenue for both the districts and the central Government.
- The Wildlife Division should come up with new modalities for hunters to acquire hunting license rather than tying license acquisition to the current system where a hunter needs to produce an ownership of gun license before a hunting license is issued.

- A major hindrance to the sustainable development of the bushmeat industry is the issues of hunting methods. There is a need to research into the current hunting methods and come up with new technologies to make it easy for hunters to get their prey without destroying the resource base of the trade.

REFERENCES

- Akumsi, A. (2003). *Community participation in wildlife management: The Mount Cameroon experience*. Proceedings of the XII World Forestry Congress, Quebec, Canada
- Asibey, E. O. A. (1966). Why not bushmeat too? *Ghana Farmer.*, 10: 165-170.
- Asibey, E.O.A., (1974a). Wildlife as a source of protein in Africa south of the Sahara. *Biological Conservation*, 6(1): 32-39.
- Asibey, E. O. A. (1974b). *Some ecological and economic aspects of the grasscutter (Tryonomys swinderianus Temminck), mammalia, rodentia (Hystricomorpha) in Ghana*. Univ. of Aberdeen. (Unpublished Ph.D. thesis).
- Asibey, E. O. A. (1974c). *The grasscutter, (Thryonomys swinderianus Temminck) in Ghana*. London: Symposium Zoological. Society. 34: 161-170.
- Asibey, E. O. A. (1978a). *Wildlife production as a means of protein supply in West Africa with particular reference to Ghana*. Proceedings of the 8th World Forestry Congress, Vol. III, p.869-881.
- Asibey, E. O. A. (1978b). *An aspect of wildlife in the life of farmers in Ghana*, Accra: Department of Game and Wildlife.
- Asibey, E. O. A. (1987). *The grasscutter*. Accra: Ghana, FAO Regional Office for Africa.
- Asibey, E. O. A. and Asare, E. O. (1978). *Range and wildlife management in Africa*. Proc. AAASA 3rd General Conference, p. 83-115. Vol. II. Ibadan, Nigeria.

- Asibey, E.O.A and Child G.S., (1990). Wildlife management for rural development in sub-Saharan Africa. *Unasylva*, (161).
- Asibey, E. O. A. and Eyeson, K. K. (1973). Additional information on the importance of wild animals as a food source in Africa south of Sahara. Bongo. *Journal of Ghana Wildlife Soc.* 1(2): 13-17.
- Azumah, D. (2002). *Finding the bushmeat balance in Ghana*. Accra: The Ghana News Agency; August.
- Bennett, E. (2002). Is there a link between wild meat and food security? *Conservation Biology*, 16: 590-592.
- Bennett, E. and Robinson, J. (2000). Hunting of wildlife in tropical forests: implications for biodiversity and forest peoples. *Biodiversity series – impact studies, Paper (76)*. Washington D.C.: Environment Department of the World Bank.
- Boafo, M. S and Falconer, J. (1997). *Facing the storm; Five years of research in around Kakum National Park, Ghana*. Kakum conservation area research colloquium in collaboration with Ghana Wildlife Department, Conservation International and the University of Cape Coast.
- Boyd, C., Blench, R., Bourn, D., Drake, L. and Stevenson P. (1999). Reconciling interests among wildlife, livestock and people in Eastern Africa: a sustainable livelihoods approach. *ODI paper (45)*, London.
- Convery, J. F. (1995). Applying environmental Economics in Africa. *Africa Technical Series; The World Bank technical paper (277)*. Washington, D.C.: The World Bank.
- Consolidated wildlife laws of Ghana, (2002). The Wildlife Division, Accra Ghana.

- Cowlishaw, G., Mendelson, S. and Rowcliffe, J.M., (2004). The bushmeat commodity chain: Patterns of trade and sustainability in a mature urban market in West Africa. *ODI wildlife policy briefing* (7). London: Zoological society of London.
- Crookes, D. J., Ankudey, N. and Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2005). The usefulness of a long-term bushmeat market dataset as an indicator of system dynamics. *Environmental Conservation* 32(4) 333–339.
- Crookes, D. J., and Milner-Gulland, E. J., (2006). Wildlife and economic policies affecting the bushmeat trade: a framework for analysis. *South African Journal of Wildlife Research* 36 (2) 159-162.
- Dei, G.J.N., (1989). Hunting and gathering in a Ghanaian rain forest community. *Ecology of Food and Nutrition* 25:29-49.
- Dei, G.J.N., (1991). The dietary habits of a Ghanaian farming community. *Ecology of Food and Nutrition* 22:45-52.
- Hazlewood, P. and Tunstall, D., (2005). *Assessing environment's contribution to poverty reduction*. Poverty-Environment Partnership. Washington D. C.: World Resources Institute, USA.
- Hladik, C. *et al.*, (1987). Se nourrir en fores équatoriale: anthropologie alimentaire différentielle des populations des régions forestières humides d Afrique. *Research Team Report* (263), Paris, CARS.
- Jachmann, H., (2007). *Monitoring law enforcement performance in nine protected areas in Ghana*. Biological conservation, ScienceDirect. [Www.Elsevier.com](http://www.Elsevier.com).
- Korang, T., (1986). *Impact of forest management on the rural population: A case-study of the Subri Project*. Kumasi: Ghana, Institute of

- Renewable Natural Resources, Univ. of Science and Technology.
(Unpublished thesis).
- Mansur, E. and Zacarias A. (2003). *From policies to practices: lessons from community forestry in Mozambique*. Proceedings of the XII World Forestry Congress, Quebec, Canada.
- Martin, G.H.G., (1983). Bushmeat in Nigeria as a natural resource with environmental implications. *Environmental Conservation*, 2: 125-132.
- Mendelson, S., Cowlshaw, G. and Rowcliffe, J. M. (2003). Anatomy of a bushmeat commodity chain in Takoradi, Ghana. *J. Peasant Stud.*31: 73–100.
- Mensah, J. (2003). *Bushmeat under threat in Ghana*. Accra: The Daily Guide Newspaper; January.
- Milius,S., (2005). *Bushmeat on the Menu; untangling the influences of hunger, wealth, and international commerce*. www.ScienceNews.org.
- Mockrin, M. H., Bennett, E. L. and LaBruna. D. T. (2005). Wildlife farming: A viable alternative to hunting in tropical forests? *Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS) Working Paper (23)*. New York: WCS.
- Ntiamoa-Baidu, Y. (1986). *Research priorities for sustainable utilisation of wildlife reserves in West Africa*. Proceedings 18th IUFRO World Congress. II, p. 687-698.
- Ntiamoa-Baidu, Y., (1998). Sustainable harvesting, production and use of bushmeat. *Wildlife development plan*, 6. Accra: Wildlife Department, Ghana.
- Wildlife Development Plan, (1998). Overview and summary. *Final draft 1*. Accra: Wildlife Department, Ghana.

- Pleydell, G. (2005). *Wildlife in Ghana; the work of the Wildlife Division*. The Forestry Commission of Ghana, Accra.
- Prins, H. H. T. and Reitsma, J. M., (1989). Mammalian biomass in an African equatorial rain forest. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 58: 851 -861.
- Reid, W.V, Mooney, H. A. and Cropper, A. (2005). *Millennium Ecosystem Assessment synthesis report*. www.millenniumassessment.org.
- Reul, R.H. (1979). Productive potential of wild animals in the tropics. *World Animal Review*, 32:18-24.
- Salafsky, N. and Margoluis, R. (2003). What conservation can learn from other fields about monitoring and evaluation. *BioScience*.53: 120–121.
- Stem, C., Margoluis, R., Salafsky, N. and Brown, M. (2005). Monitoring and evaluation in conservation: a review of trends and approaches. *Conservation Biology*.19: 295-309.
- Swenson, J. (2005). *Bushmeat trade in Techiman, Ghana, West Africa*. Uppsala: Department of Animal Ecology, Centre for Evolutionary Biology (EBC), Uppsala University, Sweden.
- Teer, J.G., (1971). *Game ranching in Texas*, p. 893-899. IUCN Pub. No. 24.
- The FAO, (1989). *Forestry and nutrition*. A reference manual Rome.
- The Forestry Commission, (1994). *Forest and Wildlife Policy*. Accra: Ministry of Lands and Forestry.
- The Living Earth Foundation, (2007). *Community resource management areas training manual*. Accra: Ghana.
- Tutu, K.A., Ntiamoah-Baidu, Y. and Asuming-Brempong, S. (1993). *The economics of living with wildlife in Ghana*. Report prepared for the World Bank, Environment Division, 85pp.

World Development Report (1992). *Development and the environment*.

Oxford: The World Bank, Oxford University Press.

APPENDIX A

Bushmeat Hunters Survey

Date.....

Locality.....

Interviewer

(Team).....

1.Name of Hunter.....

Sex.....Age.....Educational Level.....

2. Part-time or Full time (tick), if part-time what is the main occupation)?....

3. How long have you been hunting? (Give date started or estimate number of years as hunter).....

4. Information on animals killed last week

Number	Species	Number killed	Method of Capture
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			

4. What are your hunting methods?

A.....B.....

C.....D.....

5.Which of these methods do you think is the best?.....

And why?

Which of the methods is bad?.....and why?.....

7. Are you aware of any hunting regulations in Ghana?.....

If yes name them

A. Closed Season (if mentioned, period should be stated and should state allowed hunted species during the period).....

B. Prohibited hunting methods (if mentioned, should name some banned methods)

C. Prohibited hunted species (if mentioned, should name at least 3 of such species)

D. Hunting is allowed in specific areas and not others (if mentioned should name such areas) 1.Hunted areas.....2. Areas not to be hunted.....

E. License Requirements (if mentioned, should state the cost for at least three hunted species).....

I. Where do you normally get your license? (If s/he is licensed).....

II. What difficulty do you face in acquiring a licence?.....

8. What difficulty do you encounter in your hunting business?.....

Other comments.....

.....

.....

APPENDIX B

BUSHMEAT TRADERS` SURVEY

Date.....

Locality.....

Interviewer (Team).....

1.Name of Respondent

Sex.....Age.....Educational Level.....

2. Part-time or Full time (tick), if part-time what is the main occupation)?.....

3. How long have you been trading in bushmeat? (Give date started or estimate number of years as bushmeat trader).....

4. Information on animals bought on last trip

Number	Species	Number killed	Method of Capture
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			

5. Are you familiar with all the methods of hunting? Yes or No

I. Mention some of the methods, if yes.....

II. Do you buy all bushmeat irrespective of the method of capture? Yes or No (tick)

Give reason.....

III. Which of the methods of capture do you think make the best meat?.....

IV. Which of the methods fetch the highest price?

And which fetch the least price?.....

6. Are you aware of any hunting regulations in Ghana?.....

If yes name them.....

I. Closed Season (if mentioned, period should be stated and should state allowed hunted species during the period).....

II. Prohibited hunting methods (if mentioned, should name some banned methods)

III. Prohibited hunted species (if mentioned, should name at least 3 of such species)

IV. License Requirements (if mentioned, should state the cost for at least three hunted species).....

7. Where do you normally get your license? (If s/he is licensed).....

8. What difficulty do you face in acquiring a licence?.....

9. What difficulty do you encounter in your business?.....

Other comments.....

.....

APPENDIX C

**FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION WITH HUNTERS AND BUSHMEAT
TRADERS**

Date.....Locality.....Interviewer.....

No. Of Hunters () No. Of Traders ()

Sex of participants M () F()

1.Name any hunting regulations in Ghana you know.....
.....

2. Is it good to have these regulations? Yes or No.

Give reason.....

3. Which of these laws should be changed?.....

4.Which law should be added to enhance your business?.....

5. What difference does possession of license or otherwise make on your
business?

6. What are the major hindrances in licence acquisition?

.....

7. What are the major hunting methods in this area?.....

Why do people use these methods in this area?.....

.....

8.Do you know how any of these hunting methods affect the meat quality and
animal population?.....

.....

9. Does the closed season period affect your business? Yes or
No.....

Give reason.....

10. Have any of you encountered any of the law enforcement agencies concerning bushmeat? Yes or No.....

What happened and the outcome?.....

.....

Other comments.....

.....

